

REVIEW

Quality criteria for pediatric oncology centers: A systematic literature review

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Abstract

Introduction: Survival of children and adolescents diagnosed with cancer improved over the last decades due to better diagnostics, treatment, and supportive care. Quality criteria that measure, compare, and make the quality of care of individual pediatric oncology centers more transparent are heterogeneous and inconsistent.

Aim: With this systematic review, we aimed to summarize existing quality criteria for pediatric oncology centers in countries with highly developed health-care systems.

Methods: We searched three databases for publications, and websites for guidelines about quality criteria for pediatric oncology centers in February 2022. We considered all types of publications except expert opinions. We excluded publications not focusing on highly developed health-care systems, addressing the certification of professionals, or focusing on subspecialties (e.g., pediatric neuro-oncology). We discarded quality criteria if they were too specific (e.g., for a specific treatment center), too broad (e.g., national 5-year overall survival), or if the aspect was covered by standardized clinical procedures or at the national level. We grouped the identified criteria thematically.

Results: We identified 18 publications and guideline documents with 530 criteria, of which 201 fulfilled the inclusion criteria. The combination of similar criteria resulted in 90 overarching criteria, which we assigned to the following categories: facilities and networks, multidisciplinary team and other experts, supportive care, treatment, long-term care, and volume and numbers.

Conclusion: Our results provide a comprehensive overview of existing quality criteria for pediatric oncology in countries with highly developed health-care systems. These criteria can serve as a basis to develop national quality criteria in pediatric oncology.

KEYWORDS

cancer management, clinical guidelines, neoplasms, pediatric cancer

Maria Otth and Katrin Scheinemann shared last authorship.

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1 | INTRODUCTION

The survival of children and adolescents diagnosed with cancer increased markedly in countries with highly developed health-care systems.^{1–3} The 5-year survival rates over all diagnostic categories reached $\geq 85\%$, for example, in the United States,⁴ in Germany,⁵ and in Switzerland.² These survival rates reflect achievements and improvements in diagnostics, treatment, and supportive care but do not provide direct information about the quality of care delivered (e.g., rate of central venous line infections) by single treatment centers. This is, however, an important factor for the treatment centers themselves but also for the health-care systems, insurances, and most importantly, for the patients. Objectifiable and well-measurable quality criteria are necessary for this purpose.

Such quality criteria make treatment centers comparable (within and between countries), enable repeated assessments of individual centers over time, and assessable (e.g., monitoring based on the defined quality criteria) for the quality of care they provide. The extent of fulfillment of quality criteria by treatment centers can be an orientation for health-care professionals, health sector personnel less familiar with pediatric oncology (e.g., insurances), and laypersons (e.g., parents, patients, survivors). In addition, politicians and policymakers may rely on such information when establishing new laws, national care standards, or public health programs related to pediatric oncology.

Quality criteria are defined as aspects or components of processes, outcomes, or care structures that affect the quality of care.⁶ Quality criteria should be measurable, and their definition should be as clear that one can determine whether they are present or absent.^{7,8} Using quality criteria increases transparency, reflects the current standard of care nationally and internationally, and favors further improvements in the quality of care delivered.

Quality criteria for pediatric oncology centers should consider the specific aspects of pediatric cancer and pediatric patients. Besides diagnoses and treatment approaches, also the social aspects differ immensely between children and adults with cancer. Families and parents have a more active role when a child is diagnosed with cancer. In addition, the child's normal development and education are important aspects to be considered during and after treatment.

Different approaches already exist to measure quality in pediatric oncology. The German Cancer Society (Deutsche Krebsgesellschaft, DKG) offers a tool to certify German-speaking pediatric oncology centers.^{9,10} The European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOPE) provides a guideline document for European pediatric oncology centers on standards of care for children with cancer.¹¹ Additional guidelines exist for the United States and the United

Kingdom.^{12–14} In addition, different research groups developed and suggested specific quality criteria.

In this systematic review, we summarize the current evidence on quality criteria for pediatric oncology centers in countries with highly developed health-care systems. We considered countries with highly developed health-care systems to be those with good overall scores for life expectancy, avoidable mortality, population coverage, financial protection, service coverage, effective primary, preventive, and secondary care, health spending, and the number of physicians, nurses, and hospital beds as indicated by the core indicators of the “Health at Glance 2021” report.¹⁵

2 | METHODS

2.1 | Search strategy

On February 21 and 22, 2022, we systematically searched the databases PsycINFO, PubMed, and CINAHL for all types of publications published since 2000, and written in English or German. The search strategy included three concepts: quality and certification criteria, children and adolescents, and oncology (Appendix 1). We created a PubMed alert to identify newly published publications until mid of May 2022, tracked references of included publications, and checked related websites (Appendix 2). We followed the PRISMA 2020 guideline for reporting systematic reviews¹⁶ and preregistered this systematic review on PROSPERO (https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/prospero/display_record.php?ID=CRD42022308185).

2.2 | Selection of eligible publications and quality criteria

After merging the database search results, we identified and eliminated duplicate records manually (software Endnote; webtool Rayyan [<https://rayyan.ai/>; RRID:SCR_017584]).¹⁷ Two researchers (SSch and MO) independently screened titles and abstracts, full texts, and quality criteria. In case of disagreement, we consulted a third researcher (KS). We used Rayyan (<https://rayyan.ai/>; RRID:SCR_017584)¹⁷ for the title and abstract screening. We included all types of publications that mentioned quality criteria in pediatric oncology except for expert opinions. At this stage, we excluded publications focusing on adults, on the certification of professionals (e.g., nurses), or publications not targeting highly developed health-care systems. At the full-text stage, we excluded publications with $< 75\%$ of patients aged ≤ 18 years, $< 75\%$ of patients diagnosed with cancer, publications that did not clearly define, mention or apply quality criteria,

publications addressing laboratory procedures or subspecialties of pediatric oncology (e.g., radiotherapy), and publications that referred to criteria not measuring the quality of treatment centers (e.g., national 5-year survival).

Prior to data extraction, we screened the quality criteria listed in eligible publications. In accordance with exclusion criteria for publications, we did not consider quality criteria explicitly referring to adolescents and young adults (per definition >75% aged >18 years). We discarded quality criteria if they were too specific (e.g., for a specific treatment center or diagnosis), too broad (e.g., not clear how to measure the fulfillment of criteria objectively), or if they did not refer to the quality of a single center (e.g., national 5-year survival). We excluded criteria if they were covered by good clinical practice, clinical trial participation or treatment protocols (e.g., demonstration of adherence to the European Union Directive on Good Clinical Practice). We further excluded criteria if the addressed aspects were regulated nationally or if the criteria were specific for the certification of professionals or subspecialties (e.g., rehabilitation, palliative care, and bereavement). However, we considered the existence of subspecialties or access to them as criteria.

2.3 | Data extraction and critical appraisal

We extracted quality criteria and publication characteristics using standardized data extraction forms. One researcher (SSch) performed the data extractions and quality assessments of included publications, and a second researcher (MO) verified them. If criteria were reported for a specific context, we generalized them (e.g., “Included cases in treatment optimization studies of the German Society for Pediatric Oncology and Hematology (GPOH)”⁹ to “Number/Proportion of clinical trial participation”). We summarized the quality criteria thematically. Since we did not aim to summarize how the criteria can be measured, we did not extract this information.

We used the critical appraisal tools from the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI)¹⁸ to assess the selected publications' quality and risk of bias. We applied the critical appraisal checklists for cross-sectional, cohort, and qualitative studies, and for systematic reviews. Each checklist consists of eight to eleven criteria depending on the type of publication. If a publication used different methodological approaches (e.g., systematic review and qualitative part), we applied all respective checklists. As the JBI does not provide a rating scale for publication quality, we defined three quality categories. Criteria judged as “not applicable” were not considered in the quality assessment. We defined “Quality 1” if publications met all criteria, “Quality

2” if publications did not meet one or two criteria of the respective checklist, and “Quality 3” if publications did not meet three or more criteria (Table 1, Data S1).

3 | RESULTS

We identified 6179 publications from the three databases, out of which 1190 duplicates were identified and removed. The title and abstract screening resulted in 61 publications, of which 12 remained after the full-text screening. The gray literature search considered 486 additional publications, guideline documents, and websites, six of which we included in the review, resulting in a total of 18 publications/guideline documents (Figure 1, Table 1).

The most frequent reasons for exclusions at the full-text stage were: (1) publications did not mention, apply or define quality criteria, (2) <75% of the target group was aged ≤18 years, and (3) publications addressed subspecialties only (Figure 1). Two publications were assigned to “Quality 1”, three to “Quality 2”, and four to “Quality 3”. One publication used different methodological approaches (qualitative and cohort study), where one tool indicated “Quality 2” and one “Quality 3”. We did not assess the quality of the six guideline documents and two publications^{19,20} as their design did not fit any of the available checklists from the JBI critical appraisal tools (Table 1). The main reason for a reduced quality of systematic reviews was that it was unclear whether critical appraisal of included publications was conducted independently by two or more reviewers. The main reason for cohort studies was the uncertainty whether exposure was measured validly and reliably, and uncertainty whether there was congruity between the research methodology and the methods used to collect data for qualitative publications (Data S1).

The included publications comprised 530 quality criteria, of which we excluded 329 (62%). The main reasons were: (1) criteria were too broad (e.g., not clear how to measure the fulfillment of criteria objectively; 34%), (2) criteria were too specific (e.g., for a specific treatment center; 23%), or (3) that criteria did not measure the quality of care in general or for individual centers (18%) (Appendix 3).

Finally, 201 quality criteria fulfilled the inclusion criteria (Data S2). The detail accuracy differed between criteria from the different publications. The thematical grouping carried out for this reason resulted in a final set of 90 overarching criteria belonging to the following six categories: facilities and networks ($n=18$), multidisciplinary team (MDT) and other experts ($n=35$), supportive care ($n=20$), treatment ($n=12$), long-term care ($n=4$), and volume and numbers ($n=1$) (Table 2). Publications suggested relevant threshold values for

TABLE 1 Included publications and guideline documents ($n = 18$) reporting quality criteria for pediatric oncology.

First author/publisher, year, place	Publication design (method)	Outcome	Context or target group	Quality assessment ^{a,b}
Publications				
Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Health Care (IQWiG), 2005, Germany ⁴⁴ and IQWiG, 2009, Germany ⁴⁵	Report (systematic literature and clinical practice guidelines search)	Patient-relevant outcomes: survival, treatment-related death, health-related quality of life, pain, and long-term consequences of the disease and therapy	Quality of care assessment for pediatric oncology patients (acute leukemia, malignant lymphomas, and brain tumors)	SR: Quality 2
		Outcomes for procedures and infrastructure: information on standards and clinical practice guidelines, particular features of quality indicators, and organizational requirements for psychosocial support and rehabilitation		
Bradley, 2013b, Canada ²⁴	Systematic review (review of quality assessment frameworks and gray literature search; focus group to provide provisional quality indicators)	33 Quality indicators for pediatric oncology systems	Pediatric oncology system	SR: Quality 3
Bradley, 2013a, Canada ²⁵	Qualitative study (mailed survey, modified Delphi Panel Consensus Meeting)	20 Quality indicators for pediatric oncology systems	Pediatric oncology system	QR: Quality 1
Corey & Snyder, 2008, US ¹⁹	Report (plan-do-study-act cycle)	Time to antibiotics (TTA) (door/fever-to-antibiotic delivery time)	Pediatric cancer patients with febrile neutropenia	NA
de Rojas, 2019, Spain ³⁹	Retrospective cohort study (retrospective database record analysis, review of existing QIs in other areas of oncology, national, and consensus documents)	34 Quality indicators for pediatric CNS tumors	Pediatric medulloblastoma patients	CS: Quality 3
		How defined quality indicators are met in the audit; outcome given by the quality indicators for pediatric CNS tumors		
Fletcher, 2013, US ²²	Retrospective cohort study (retrospective patient record analysis, TTA measured as a continuous variable and in 60 min intervals)	Association of TTA administration with outcomes of febrile neutropenia in pediatric oncology patients. Outcomes: in-hospital mortality, pediatric intensive care unit admission within 24 h of presentation, fluid resuscitation 40 mL/kg within 24 h of presentation, length of stay	Pediatric oncology patients with febrile neutropenia	CS: Quality 2
Knops, 2012, The Netherlands ²⁹	Literature review and qualitative study (RAND modified Delphi method)	Recommendations for "process" and "structure" of medical care in pediatric oncology	Pediatric oncology patients	SR: Quality 3 QR: Quality 2
Knops, 2013, The Netherlands ²³	Systematic review (database search and reference tracking)	Quality of care or survival in childhood cancer	Hospital volume, pediatric oncology patients	SR: Quality 1

TABLE 1 (Continued)

First author/publisher, year, place	Publication design (method)	Outcome	Context or target group	Quality assessment ^{a,b}
McCavit & Winick, 2012, Canada and US (survey within the Children's Oncology Group) ²¹	Brief report (electronic survey)	Proportion of centers tracking TTA as a quality-of-care measure, respondents' TTA benchmark/standard, locations where TTA is collected (inpatient unit, outpatient clinic, or emergency department), most recent TTA data from each respondent	Pediatric oncology patients with febrile neutropenia	CSS: Quality 2
Olshelski, 2020, US ²⁰	Original article (development and test of Cancer Care Index; retrospective and real-time, multidisciplinary microsystem-based teams addressed specific aims for each domain)	Cancer Care Index and the impact of its application on quality and safety performance	Oncology-bone marrow transplant service	NA
Teichman, 2017, Canada ⁴⁶	Literature search, qualitative study (de novo development by a steering committee, Delphi process)	Quality metrics for a leukemia-lymphoma clinic	Pediatric patients diagnosed with leukemia or lymphoma, outpatient setting	QR: Quality 2
ten Berg, 2018, The Netherlands ⁴⁷	Qualitative study, retrospective cohort study (consensus process questionnaire, patient records)	Seven structure, process, and outcome indicators developed based on Dutch Childhood Oncology Group guidelines	Pediatric oncology patients with febrile neutropenia	QR: Quality 3 CS: Quality 3
Guideline documents				
National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE), 2005, UK ¹³	Guidance on cancer service—the Manual		Pediatric oncology	NA
NICE, 2014, UK ¹⁴	Quality standard		Pediatric oncology	NA
Federal Joint Committee (G-BA), 2021, Germany ⁴⁸	Guideline		Pediatric oncology	NA
German Cancer Society (DKG), 2021, Germany ⁹	Certification survey form		Pediatric oncology	NA
The European Society for paediatric oncology (SIOPE); Kowalczyk, 2009, Europe ¹¹	Standards of care		Pediatric oncology	NA
American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP); Hord, 2014, US ¹²	Policy statement: Guidelines for Pediatric Cancer Centers		Pediatric oncology	NA

Abbreviations: AAP, American Academy of Pediatrics; DKG, German Cancer Society (Deutsche Krebsgesellschaft); G-BA, Federal Joint Committee (Gemeinsamer Bundesausschuss); IQWiG, Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Health Care (Institut für Qualität und Wirtschaftlichkeit im Gesundheitswesen); NICE, National Institute for Health and Care Excellence; SIOPE, The European Society for paediatric oncology; TTA, time to antibiotics.

^aAbbreviations for the type of critical appraisal tools used for quality assessment: SR checklist for systematic reviews, QR checklist for qualitative research, CS checklist for cohort studies, CSS checklist for analytical cross-sectional Studies, NA not applicable.

^bFor details, see Data S1.

FIGURE 1 PRISMA 2020 flow diagram of included publications and guidelines.^{16 †}Reference tracking of included publications and searching related websites. [‡]Children defined as ≤ 18 years of age.

some quality criteria. For the criterion “time to antibiotic (TTA) administration” in patients with febrile neutropenia (“Supportive Care” category), publications mentioned benchmarks of 30^{19,21} or 60 min.^{20–22} For the criterion “number of cases per year and provider/clinic”, publications suggested ≥ 5 cases/year/provider as a high volume²³ or 30 new cases/year/unit as a minimum.¹¹ Stated thresholds for other criteria are listed in the table of included quality criteria in their original detailed version (Data S2).

4 | DISCUSSION

We could identify 90 quality criteria belonging to six thematic categories. Even though the identified criteria were heterogeneous, for example, related to the scope (some criteria for specific centers or disciplines only), they can serve as a basis for developing uniform and harmonized quality criteria for pediatric oncology centers in different countries.

Bradley et al. identified a set of quality criteria specific to Canadian pediatric oncology.^{24,25} Many of their criteria refer to the Pediatric Oncology Group of Ontario (POGO)

and to their satellite system institutions. POGO is a non-profit organization (and the official advisor to the Ontario Ministry of Health on childhood cancer care and treatment) and works to ensure that everyone with pediatric cancer has access to the best care and support.²⁶ Even though the quality criteria of this publication focus on the POGO system, we included its results in a generalized form.

Though heterogeneous, the criteria of the different publications in all six categories have also resembled and complemented each other. For the criteria on facilities and networks, eligible publications provided different levels of detail of single facilities but finally did not differ much regarding the main components. Even though we focused on general quality criteria, some might not be relevant for pediatric oncology centers in certain countries. For example, the criterion on reporting to the “childhood cancer registry” is only applicable for centers where cancer registration is not common practice. In countries where pediatric cancer registries cover the national population (e.g., Hungary, Greece, Germany, France, Belarus, Czech Republic, and the United Kingdom²⁷) or registration is mandatory (e.g., Switzerland²⁸), the fulfillment of this criterion might be less meaningful.

Most criteria related to MDT addressed disciplines and specialists with expertise in the pediatric field that

TABLE 2 List of summarized quality criteria for pediatric oncology centers by thematical categories.

Facilities and networks		
Access to the following important facilities		
Pharmacy ^{12,29,48}	Microbiology Institute ⁴⁸	Pediatric cardiology ⁴⁸
Adult hematology and oncology ⁴⁸	Laboratories ^{11,12,29,48} : hematology, hematopathology, clinical chemistry, transfusion	Pathology ^{29,48}
Orthopedics ⁴⁸	Pediatric intensive care unit ^{29,48}	Pediatric radiology ^{12,29,48}
Stem cell transplant unit ¹²	Pediatric nephrology ^{12,29,48}	Radiation therapy ^{12,20,29,48}
Pediatric surgery ^{29,48}	Pediatric neurosurgery ^{13,29,48}	Nuclear medicine ⁴⁸
Pediatric anesthetics ²⁹	Hospital hygiene ⁴⁸	Childhood cancer registry ^{9,11,29}
Multidisciplinary team (MDT) and other experts		
MDT established, including regularly scheduled MDT conferences ^{9,11–13,29,48}	Number of pediatric oncology disciplines with multidisciplinary staffing ratios for pediatric oncology ^{13,24,25,29,48}	
An MDT should consist of representatives from the following disciplines/expertise (disciplines involved depend on the patients' needs)		
Pediatric oncology practitioner-in-charge/lead clinician (also with expertise in late effects) ^{13,29}	Pediatric oncologists ^{11–13,48}	Pediatric oncology nurses ^{11–13,48}
Pediatric radiologists ^{12,13,29}	Pediatric surgeons ^{12,13,29}	Radiation oncologists ^{12,29}
Pediatric endocrinologist ^{12,13}	Pediatric critical care specialists ^{12,29}	Pediatric infectious diseases specialists ¹²
Pediatric anesthesiology ^{12,29}	Pediatric cardiologist ^{12,29}	Pediatric neurologist ^{12,29}
Pediatric gastroenterologist ^{12,29}	Pediatric nephrologist ^{12,29}	Pediatric pulmonologist ^{12,29}
Ear–nose–throat specialist ²⁹	Ophthalmologist ²⁹	Long-term care (experts) ²⁹
Genetics specialists ^{12,29}	Pain management experts ²⁹	Palliative care specialists ^{12,13,29}
Complementary and alternative therapies ¹²	Dieticians ^{11,12,48}	Occupational therapists ^{11,48}
Rehabilitation specialists ^{11,12}	Pharmacists experienced in chemotherapy preparation ^{12,13}	Laboratory technicians ¹¹
Medical secretaries and data managers ¹¹	Dentist ¹²	Psychosocial care/services ^{11–13,29,48}
Ward teachers ^{11–13}	Activity/play therapy staff ^{11,13,29}	Pediatric pathologist ^{12,13,29}
Supportive care		
Central venous catheter (CVC)		
Complication rates: particularly the incidence of CVC-associated infection ^{13,24}	Surgical complication rates (failure to insert the desired device or leaving the catheter tip in an unacceptable location) related to CVC placement ²⁰	Written policies/ procedures for the management of CVC ^{24,25}
Existence of supportive care guidelines ^{24,25,29} including supportive care (guidelines) for		
Nausea, vomiting and bowel disturbance ^{13,24,25}	Nutritional assessment ^{13,20,24,29}	Fertility (preservation) discussion ^{14,20,29}
Palliative care (including bereavement) ^{11,13,24,29,39}	(Neuro-) Rehabilitation ^{11,13,14}	Dental care ¹³
Pain relief, including local protocol for pain relief procedures and adequate pain management ^{13,24,25,44–46}	Psychological or psychosocial care, including provision of/information about social care ^{9,11,13,14,20,44,45,48}	Provision of school education ^{11,20,29}
Provision of cancer education ¹²		

(Continues)

TABLE 2 (Continued)

Supportive care		
Febrile neutropenia (F&N)		
Guidelines on how to approach a child with F&N (availability, risk-stratified approach, escalation for fever persistence) ^{13,24,25,47}	Number/proportion of clinical F&N episodes in which the patients with or without microbial focus are treated with first line antibiotics according to local guidelines ⁴⁷	Number/proportion of clinical F&N episodes in which patients are admitted to ICU ⁴⁷
Number/proportion of clinical F&N episodes in which the patient died ⁴⁷	Number/proportion of fungal health care-associated infections ²⁰	Time to antibiotics (TTA) administration ^{19–22}
Treatment		
Number/proportion of patients presented in the interdisciplinary tumor conference (for solid and liquid tumors separately or combined) ^{9,12,24,48}	Protocol compliance (e.g., number of major clinical trial protocol violations) ^{13,24,39}	Number/proportion of clinical trial participation ^{9,13,14,24,25,29,39}
Number/proportion of refusal and failure to complete treatment ¹³		
Delay in/ wait time to start of Radiotherapy ¹³	Chemotherapy ^{13,24,25}	First therapeutic intervention ^{24,25}
Release of pathology results ^{13,24,25}		
Medication		
Number/proportion of patient safety incidents related to chemotherapy prescriptions ¹⁴	Number/proportion of actual drug or dose errors identified for patients on active treatment ^{13,24,25}	Number/proportion of potential drug or dose errors identified for patients on active treatment ^{13,24,25}
Number/Proportion of elective pediatric oncology ambulatory procedures requiring anesthesia that are deferred to the next day or beyond due to resource limitation(s) ^{24,25}		
Long-term care		
Number/proportion of survivors of childhood cancer with a survivor care plan ^{13,14,24,25,29}	Number/proportion of survivors who have their survivorship care plan reviewed 5 years after the end of treatment ¹⁴	Established follow-up structure ^{11,13,24,25}
Established transition structure ^{12,29}		
Volume and numbers		
Number of cases per year and provider/clinic ^{9,11,23,39}		

should be part of these teams. As children and adolescents have different needs than adults, one should consider the pediatric competence of MDT members when defining quality criteria. Even though not stated explicitly in the included publications, the expertise of an MDT differs depending on the patients' needs and underlying diagnosis. Further, an MDT should be led by a person responsible for and coordinating the different involved disciplines.^{13,29} The content of protocols from MDT meetings was not specified, which might be a relevant quality criterion too.

Quality criteria on supportive care covered the topics of specific supportive care disciplines, guidelines (e.g., for rehabilitation), central venous catheters (CVC), and febrile neutropenia. Two publications mentioned the "CVC-associated infection rate" as a quality criterion.^{13,24} This is an important measure in daily clinical practice, and additional publications examined different improvement approaches to prevent and reduce CVC-associated infections.^{30–32} Duffy et al. examined, for example, the effect of a CVC care bundle consisting of several tasks (e.g., standardized hand hygiene or change of dressings) on the

frequency of CVC-associated infections.³¹ “TTA administration” seems to be another well-established criterion for pediatric oncology patients with febrile neutropenia. Besides the included publications mentioning TTA as a quality criterion, several researchers addressed how to reduce TTA in patients with febrile neutropenia in inpatient,³³ intensive care,³⁴ or emergency departments.^{35–37} When using TTA as a quality criterion, it is essential to define a clear starting point. Taking the time from first measured fever might be difficult in the outpatient setting as the time to the hospital differs between patients, depending on the living distance from the hospital. The resulting difference in travel time to the hospital has an impact on the TTA, which cannot be influenced by the quality of the center itself. The starting point on admission to the hospital (emergency room or ward) would therefore be more indicative of the quality of the pediatric oncology center.

Quantifying “Fungal Health Care-Associated Infections” in patients with febrile neutropenia was another quality criterion.²⁰ This is a relevant measure as invasive fungal infections are dangerous for immunocompromised patients.³⁸ However, a general monitoring system for all pathogens, including viral, bacterial, and fungal infections, could be favored over the monitoring of fungal pathogens only. Knowing the local microbiological spectrum can help pediatric oncology centers in the selection of the appropriate empiric antibiotic treatment in case of febrile neutropenia. It may further help to identify local environmental factors (e.g., an increase in invasive aspergillosis in areas with construction work). Both factors increase the quality of care.

In the category “treatment”, one could favor time-related criteria. However, defining generalized thresholds, for example, for the criteria “first therapeutic intervention” or the “release of the pathology results” could be problematic as the time taken depends strongly on the diagnosis and required analyses. While the results for leukemia can be provided relatively quickly, it requires more time for bone tumors, where the tissue must first be decalcified. Such aspects need to be considered when assessing the treatment quality of a center with time-related criteria and might result in many separate criteria.

Different publications mentioned the “number of cases per year and provider/clinic”^{9,11,23,39} in the category volume and numbers. However, it is unclear whether a higher volume indicates better quality of care. A retrospective cohort study found no association between a low case volume and increased mortality or intensive care unit (ICU) admission in pediatric acute lymphoblastic leukemia patients.⁴⁰ Another publication also did not find a difference in survival between centers of bigger and smaller sizes for pediatric neuro-oncology patients.⁴¹ Besides, by measuring the quality of care quantitatively, relevant qualitative

aspects, such as the provision of various supportive care services that contribute to the quality of care, are neglected. Previous research also questioned the evidence of thresholds and the generalizability of using patient numbers for assessing the quality of care in Germany.⁴²

Many pediatric oncology centers are grown historically, for example, based on geographic location or because pediatric oncologists initially worked there, but not based on the provided quality. Therefore, quality criteria can be used as an orientation in monitoring the existing centers, but also to increase or decrease the number of centers, depending on the current national situation. For example, centers can check which facilities should be established, which representatives an MDT should consist of, and which supportive care areas they should cover. Audits can check the fulfillment of quality criteria when assessing pediatric oncology centers. For accreditation of centers, the quality criteria identified in this review could be included in surveillance software or hospital systems for pediatric oncology centers, which ministries of health and other relevant players can access. The extent of compliance to the criteria could be made publicly available and could help different stakeholders to advocate for equal access and care within a country and to address shortcomings on national and political levels. Further, if centers cannot meet quality criteria, health ministries could help to allocate resources to these centers to improve care quality. Overall, applying uniform quality criteria can increase the transparency and comparability of centers within and between countries. However, the list of quality criteria provided in this review needs to be cautiously applied. Differences in health-care systems between countries necessitate adapting the quality criteria to the national needs and circumstances.

4.1 | Strengths and limitations

The strength of this review is that we searched three databases and considered almost all publication types published over more than 20 years. In addition, we tracked references and searched gray literature. Further, the title and abstract screening, full-text screening, data extraction, and quality assessment were performed by two researchers. A limitation inherent to systematic literature reviews is that we might have missed criteria that are considered quality criteria which, however, were not named as such in the literature. The same is true for criteria used at national levels, which are not publicly available. The external validity of this list of quality criteria may be limited by the fact that it applies to countries with highly developed health-care systems, as quality criteria for countries with less developed health-care systems need to address more

fundamental aspects of care. However, other publications explicitly focus on quality criteria for pediatric oncology in countries with less developed health-care systems.⁴³

5 | CONCLUSION

The list of quality criteria provided by this systematic review can serve as a basis to develop national sets of quality criteria or assessment tools for pediatric oncology centers in highly developed health-care systems. To select a relevant subset of criteria adapted to national circumstances, experts should qualitatively discuss and evaluate the criteria and state uniform measurements in future research.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Sarah P. Schladerer: Formal analysis (lead); investigation (lead); methodology (lead); project administration (supporting); visualization (lead); writing – original draft (lead); writing – review and editing (lead). **Maria Otth:** Conceptualization (supporting); formal analysis (supporting); funding acquisition (supporting); investigation (supporting); methodology (supporting); project administration (supporting); supervision (supporting); writing – original draft (supporting); writing – review and editing (supporting). **Katrin Scheinemann:** Conceptualization (lead); formal analysis (supporting); funding acquisition (lead); investigation (supporting); methodology (supporting); project administration (lead); supervision (lead); writing – original draft (supporting); writing – review and editing (supporting).

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

There are no conflicts of interest for any of the authors.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

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APPENDIX 1**Database (PubMed, CINAHL, PsycINFO) search strategy.**

Concept 1: Quality and certification criteria.

Concept 2: Children and adolescents.

Concept 3: Oncology.

PubMed Search (performed on February 22nd, 2022)

#1	“Quality Indicators, Health Care”[MeSH]
#2	quality of care [tiab] OR quality indicator* [tiab] OR quality measure* [tiab] OR quality marker* [tiab] OR quality improvement* [tiab] OR quality appraisal* [tiab] OR certification* [tiab] OR performance indicator*[tiab] OR performance metric* [tiab] OR performance measure* [tiab] OR standard of care [tiab] OR standards of care [tiab]
#3	“Child”[MesH] OR “Pediatrics”[Mesh] OR “Infant”[MesH] OR “Adolescent”[MesH]
#4	child*[tiab] OR infan*[tiab] OR adolescen*[tiab] OR newborn*[tiab] OR baby*[tiab] OR babies[tiab] OR neonat*[tiab] OR perinat*[tiab] OR postnat*[tiab] OR schoolchild*[tiab] OR school child*[tiab] OR kid[tiab] OR kids[tiab] OR toddler*[tiab] OR teen*[tiab] OR boy[tiab] OR boys [tiab] OR girl*[tiab] OR juvenil*[tiab] OR youth*[tiab] OR kindergar*[tiab] OR pediatric*[tiab] OR paediatric*[tiab] OR school*[tiab] OR preschool*[tiab] OR pre school*[tiab] OR elementary school*[tiab] OR highschool*[tiab] OR high school*[tiab] OR schoolage*[tiab] OR school age*[tiab]
#5	“Neoplasms”[MesH] OR “Oncology Service, Hospital”[Mesh] OR “Cancer Care Facilities”[Mesh]
#6	cancer* [tiab] OR oncolog* [tiab] OR neoplasm*[tiab] OR carcinom* [tiab] OR tumor* [tiab] OR tumour*[tiab] OR malignan*[tiab] OR hematooncological [tiab] OR hemato oncologic*[tiab] OR hematologic neoplasm* [tiab] OR hematolo*[tiab]
#7	all [sb] “Animals”[Mesh] NOT “Humans”[Mesh]
#8	“english”[Language]
#9	“german”[Language]
#10	(“2000/01/01”[Date - Publication]: “2022”[Date - Publication])
#11	#1 OR #2
#12	#3 OR #4
#13	#5 OR #6
#14	#11 AND #12 AND #13
#15	#14 NOT #7
#16	#8 OR #9
#17	#15 AND #16
#18	#17 AND #10

CINAHL Search (performed on February 22nd, 2022)

Search ID#	Search terms
S1	(MH “Quality Assurance+”)
S2	TI ((quality W3 care) OR (quality W1 indicator*) OR (quality W1 measure*) OR (quality marker*) OR (quality improvement*) OR (quality W1 appraisal*) OR (certification*) OR (performance W1 indicator*) OR (performance W1 metric*) OR (performance W1 measure*) OR (standard N3 care) OR (standards N3 care)) OR AB ((quality W3 care) OR (quality N4 indicator*) OR (quality W1 measure*) OR (quality marker*) OR (quality improvement*) OR (quality W1 appraisal*) OR (certification*) OR (performance W1 indicator*) OR (performance W1 metric*) OR (performance W1 measure*) OR (standard N3 care) OR (standards N3 care))
S3	(MH “Child+”) OR (MH “Infant+”) OR (MH “Adolescence+”) OR (MH “Pediatrics+”)
S4	TI ((child*) OR (infan*) OR (adolescen*) OR (new W1 born*) OR (baby) OR (babies) OR (neonat*) OR (perinat*) OR (postnat*) OR (school W1 child*) OR (toddler*) OR (teen*) OR (boy*) OR (girl*) OR (youth*) OR (kindergar*) OR (p#ediatric*) OR (school*) OR (preschool*) OR (pre W1 school*) OR (elementary W1 school*) OR (highschool*) OR (high W1 school*) OR (schoolage*) OR (school W1 age*)) OR AB ((child*) OR (infan*) OR (adolescen*) OR (new W1 born*) OR (baby) OR (babies) OR (neonat*) OR (perinat*) OR (postnat*) OR (school W1 child*) OR (toddler*) OR (teen*) OR (boy*) OR (girl*) OR (youth*) OR (young W2 adult*) OR (kindergar*) OR (p#ediatric*) OR (school*) OR (preschool*) OR (pre W1 school*) OR (elementary W1 school*) OR (highschool*) OR (high W1 school*) OR (schoolage*) OR (school W1 age*))
S5	(MH “Neoplasms+”) OR (MM “Cancer Care Facilities”) OR (MM “Oncology Care Units”) OR (MM “Childhood Neoplasms”)

APPENDIX 1 (Continued)

CINAHL Search (performed on February 22nd, 2022)	
Search ID#	Search terms
S6	TI ((cancer*) OR (oncolog*) OR (neoplasm*) OR (carcinom*) OR (tumo#r*) OR (malignan*) OR (hematooncological) OR (hemato W1 oncological) OR (hematologic W1 neoplasm*) OR (hematolo*)) OR AB ((cancer*) OR (oncolog*) OR (neoplasm*) OR (carcinom*) OR (tumo#r*) OR (malignan*) OR (hematooncological) OR (hemato W1 oncological) OR (hematologic W1 neoplasm*) OR (hematolo*))
S7	(MH "Animals+" not MH "Humans+")
S8	LA German
S9	LA English
S10	PY 2000–2022
S11	S1 OR S2
S12	S3 OR S4
S13	S5 OR S6
S14	S11 AND S12 AND S13
S15	S14 NOT S7
S16	S8 OR S9
S17	S15 AND S16
S18	S10 AND S17
PsycINFO Search (performed on February 21st, 2022)	
S1	MAINSUBJECT.EXACT.EXPLODE ("Quality of Care") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT ("Quality Control")
S2	Ti,AB ("quality of care" OR ("quality indicator" OR "quality indicators") OR ("quality measure" OR "quality measurement" OR "quality measurements" OR "quality measures") OR "quality marker*" OR ("quality improvement" OR "quality improvements") OR "quality appraisal*" OR certification* OR ("performance indicator" OR "performance indicators") OR ("performance metric" OR "performance metrics") ("performance measure" OR "performance measured" OR "performance measurement" OR "performance measurements" OR "performance measures") OR "standard* of care")
S3	MAINSUBJECT.EXACT.EXPLODE ("Pediatrics") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT.EXPLODE ("Adolescent Health")
S4	Ti,AB (child* OR infan* OR adolescen* OR ("new born" OR "new borns") OR baby OR babies OR neonat* OR perinat* OR postnat* OR ("school child" OR "school childcare" OR "school children") OR toddler* OR teen* OR boy* OR girl* OR youth* OR kindergar* OR pediatric* OR paediatric* OR school* OR preschool* OR ("pre school" OR "pre schooler" OR "pre schoolers" OR "pre schools") OR ("elementary school" OR "elementary schoolchildren" OR "elementary schoolhome" OR "elementary schooling" OR "elementary schoolk" OR "elementary schools" OR "elementary schoolteacher") OR highschool* OR ("high school" OR "high schooler" OR "high schoolers" OR "high schoolin" OR "high schooling" OR "high schools" OR "high schoolthe") OR schoolage* OR ("school age" OR "school aged" OR "school ages")
S5	MAINSUBJECT.EXACT.EXPLODE ("Neoplasms")
S6	Ti,AB (cancer* OR oncolog* OR neoplasm* OR carcinom* OR tumor* OR tumour* OR malignan* OR hematooncological OR "hemato oncological" OR "hematologic neoplasm*" OR hematolo*)
S7	LA (english)
S8	LA (german)
S9	YR (2000-2022)
S10	S1 OR S2
S11	S3 OR S4
S12	S5 OR S6
S13	S10 AND S11 AND S12
S14	S7 OR S8
S15	S13 AND S14
S16	S15 AND S9
S17	S16 AND (styp.e.exact ("Scholarly Journals"))
S18	S17 AND PEER (yes))

APPENDIX 2

Websites accessed within the gray literature search.

Website	Reason for exclusion or comment	Quality criteria extracted from the website
https://www.aonnonline.org/31-aonn/223-aonn-evidence-based-navigation-metrics	Did not clearly define, mention, or apply quality criteria for pediatric oncology	No
https://ukneqas.org.uk/	Addressed laboratory procedures	No
NQF: Quality Positioning System™ (qualityforum.org)	Reasons for exclusion of criteria: < 75% of the diagnosis were cancer diagnosis, < 75% of target population were aged ≤18 years, or too specific	No
https://www.stjude.org/global/sjcares/profile.html	No response to an email request (Contacted to request the PrOFiLE Tool)	No
https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/qs55/chapter/Quality-statement-1-Multidisciplinary-teams-for-young-people	Retrieved one report from the website (NICE, 2014)	Yes, from a report (NICE, 2014) found on this website

APPENDIX 3

Numbers and proportions of excluded criteria by exclusion reason.

Exclusion reason	Number of excluded criteria	Proportion of all excluded criteria (n = 329) in %
Too broad (e.g., not clear how to measure the fulfillment of criteria objectively)	113	34.35
Too specific (e.g., for a specific treatment center or diagnosis)	75	22.8
Does not measure the quality of care or at least not at only an individual center	59	17.93
Covered by good clinical practice	17	5.17
Covered by clinical trial participation or treatment protocols	29	8.81
Regulated nationally	23	6.99
Related to the certification of professionals or specialties	8	2.43
Given by MDT (e.g., “In case of a necessary interim consultation about a patient an extra meeting of the MDT with all its members should be arranged within one working day.” (Knops et al., 2012))	3	0.91
Not an outcome of the study (e.g., “rates of chemotherapy errors” (McCavit & Winick, 2012) mentioned in the discussion of an article but not in the results or major topic of this article)	2	0.61
Total	329	100

Supporting Information 1 Quality assessments of included publications using the critical appraisal tools of the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) (<https://jbi.global/critical-appraisal-tools>)

CHECKLIST FOR SYSTEMATIC REVIEWS AND RESEARCH SYNTHESSES												
First author or publisher (Year)	Is the review question clearly and explicitly stated?	Were the inclusion criteria appropriate for the review question?	Was the search strategy appropriate?	Were the sources and resources used to search for studies adequate?	Were the criteria for appraising studies appropriate?	Was critical appraisal conducted by two or more reviewers independently?	Were there methods to minimize errors in data extraction?	Were the methods used to combine studies appropriate?	Was the likelihood of publication bias assessed?	Were recommendations for policy and/or practice supported by the reported data?	Were the specific directives for new research appropriate?	Total quality category
IQWiG (2005, 2009)	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	unclear	yes	yes	not applicable	yes	yes	Quality 2
Bradley (2013)	yes	yes	yes	yes	unclear	unclear	unclear	not applicable	not applicable	yes	yes	Quality 3
Knops (2012)	yes	yes	yes	yes	unclear	unclear	no	yes	not applicable	yes	yes	Quality 3
Knops (2013)	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	not applicable	yes	yes	Quality 1
CHECKLIST FOR QUALITATIVE RESEARCH												
First author or publisher (Year)	Is there congruity between the stated philosophical perspective and the research methodology?	Is there congruity between the research methodology and the research question or objectives?	Is there congruity between the research methodology and the methods used to collect data?	Is there congruity between the research methodology and the representation and analysis of data?	Is there congruity between the research methodology and the interpretation of results?	Is there a statement locating the researcher culturally or theoretically?	Is the influence of the researcher on the research, and vice-versa, addressed?	Are participants, and their voices, adequately represented?	Is the research ethical according to current criteria or, for recent studies, and is there evidence of ethical approval by an appropriate body?	Do the conclusions drawn in the research report flow from the analysis, or interpretation, of the data?	Total quality category	
Bradley (2013)	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	not applicable	not applicable	yes	yes	yes	Quality 1	
Knops (2012)	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	not applicable	no	yes	yes	yes	Quality 2	
Teichman (2017)	yes	yes	unclear	yes	yes	not applicable	not applicable	yes	yes	yes	Quality 2	
ten Berg (2018)	yes	yes	unclear	unclear	yes	not applicable	yes	unclear	yes	yes	Quality 3	
CHECKLIST FOR COHORT STUDIES												
First author or publisher (Year)	Were the two groups similar and recruited from the	Were the exposures measured similarly to assign	Was the exposure measured in a valid and	Were confounding factors identified?	Were strategies to deal with confounding	Were the groups/participants free of the outcome at the start of the	Were the outcomes measured in a valid and	Were the follow up time reported and sufficient to be long	Was the follow up complete, and if not, were the	Were strategies to address incomplete	Was appropriate statistical analysis used?	Total quality category

	same population?	people to both exposed and unexposed groups?	reliable way?		factors stated?	study (or at the moment of exposure)?	reliable way?	enough for outcomes to occur?	reasons to loss to follow up described and explored?	follow up utilized?		
de Rojas (2019)	not applicable	not applicable	unclear	unclear	unclear	not applicable	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	Quality 3
Fletcher (2013)	not applicable	not applicable	unclear	yes	yes	not applicable	yes	not applicable	yes	not applicable	yes	Quality 2
ten Berg (2018)	not applicable	not applicable	yes	no	yes	not applicable	unclear	not applicable	no	not applicable	yes	Quality 3
CHECKLIST FOR ANALYTICAL CROSS SECTIONAL STUDIES												
First author or publisher (Year)	Were the criteria for inclusion in the sample clearly defined?	Were the study subjects and the setting described in detail?	Was the exposure measured in a valid and reliable way?	Were objective, standard criteria used for measurement of the condition?	Were confounding factors identified?	Were strategies to deal with confounding factors stated?	Were the outcomes measured in a valid and reliable way?	Was appropriate statistical analysis used?	Total quality category			
McCavit & Winick (2012)	yes	yes	not applicable	yes	no	no	yes	yes	Quality 2			

Supporting Information 2 Included quality criteria in their original detailed version

Publisher or first author (year)[†]	Original criterion	Description or measurement	Summarized criterion/criteria
Facilities and networks			
G-BA (2021) ¹	Pharmacy with centralized cytostatic preparation available on a daily basis if needed.	yes/no	Pharmacy
Hord (2014) ²	A pharmacy capable of accurate, well-monitored preparation and dispensing of antineoplastic agents and investigational agents		Pharmacy
Knops (2012) ³	In a paediatric oncology centre, the following facilities are daily, including weekends, available between 8.00 and 18.00 o'clock: Pharmacy with central preparation of cytostatics Microbiology laboratory Pathology laboratory (for morphologic, immunohistochemic and genetic tumour diagnostics) Hospital catering		Pharmacy Laboratories
G-BA (2021) ¹	Hematology laboratory with the possibility of cytological blood and bone marrow examinations with special cytochemical stains	yes/no	Laboratories
Hord (2014) ²	An established relationship with a hematopathology laboratory capable of performing cell-phenotype analysis using flow cytometry, immunohistochemistry, molecular diagnosis, cytogenetics, and polymerase chain reaction–based methodology and fluorescence in situ hybridization		Laboratories
Hord (2014) ²	A clinical chemistry laboratory with the capability to monitor antibiotic and antineoplastic drug concentration		Laboratories
Hord (2014) ²	A blood bank capable of providing a full range of products, including irradiated and leuko-depleted blood components		Laboratories
Kowalczyk (2009) ⁴	Requirements of a Paediatric Haematology and/or Oncology Unit	The unit should have similar availability of blood products especially blood, platelets, and commonly-used protein fractions.	Laboratories
G-BA (2021) ¹	Laboratory Medicine or Clinical Chemistry Laboratory	yes/no	Laboratories
G-BA (2021) ¹	Transfusion Medicine	yes/no	Laboratories
G-BA (2021) ¹	Microbiology Institute	yes/no	Microbiology Institute
G-BA (2021) ¹	Cardiology	yes/no	Pediatric cardiology
G-BA (2021) ¹	Internal hematology and oncology	yes/no	Adult hematology and oncology

G-BA (2021) ¹	The facilities required for emergency care (intensive care facility, emergency laboratory, transfusion medicine, conventional X-ray diagnostics and sonography; CT or MRI) are provided at the center	yes/no	Pediatric intensive care unit Laboratories Pediatric radiology
G-BA (2021) ¹	Intensive care facility for pediatric patients accessible without patient transport outside the hospital's own grounds (with capability for mechanical ventilation and acute renal replacement procedures; and blood exchange or leukapheresis)	yes/no	Pediatric intensive care unit
Hord (2014) ²	Up-to-date diagnostic imaging facilities to perform radiography, computed tomography, MRI, ultra-sonography, radionuclide imaging, and angiography; positron-emission tomography scanning and other emerging technologies are desirable		Pediatric radiology
G-BA (2021) ¹	Advanced imaging diagnostics with the option of anesthesia/sedation examinations (accessible without patient transport outside the clinic's own premises)	yes/no	Pediatric radiology
G-BA (2021) ¹	Institute of Pathology	yes/no	Pathology
G-BA (2021) ¹	Hospital Hygiene	yes/no	Hospital hygiene
G-BA (2021) ¹	Orthopedics	yes/no	Orthopedics
G-BA (2021) ¹	Nuclear Medicine Clinic	yes/no	Nuclear medicine
DKG (2022/2021) ⁵	Reporting cases to childhood cancer registry/central database	Indicator target: reporting of all primary cases to the national childhood cancer registry. Numerator: primary cases of the denominator reported to the childhood cancer registry Denominator: primary cases with national residency. Target: $\geq 95\%$	Childhood cancer registry
Kowalczyk (2009) ⁴	National Register of Childhood Cancer	Population-based cancer registration	Childhood cancer registry
Knops (2012) ³	In a paediatric oncology centre the diagnoses that belong specifically to the field of paediatric oncology will be reported to a central database.	Recommendation	Childhood cancer registry
Hord (2014) ²	Access to stem cell transplant services with the capability or availability of HLA antigen typing		Stem cell transplant unit
Hord (2014) ²	Access within the community to pediatric hemodialysis and/or hemofiltration and apheresis		Pediatric nephrology
G-BA (2021) ¹	Nephrology with dialysis	yes/no	Pediatric nephrology
Hord (2014) ²	Access to up-to-date radiationtherapy equipment with facilities for treating pediatric patients		Radiation therapy
G-BA (2021) ¹	Radiotherapy with radiooncological procedures in line with technical progress	yes/no	Radiation therapy

Olshefski (2020) ⁶	Pediatric anesthesiology for radiation oncology	When radiation therapy is delivered at an adult-oriented site outside the primary hospital: optimal anesthesia-related care for sedation of these children requires a provider with pediatric training. The cancer care index tracks patients requiring sedation for radiation therapy managed by an anesthesiologist without extensive pediatric training	Radiation therapy
G-BA (2021) ¹	Pediatric Surgery	yes/no	Pediatric surgery
G-BA (2021) ¹	Surgery	yes/no	Pediatric surgery
Kowalczyk (2009) ⁴	Requirements of a Paediatric Haematology and/or Oncology Unit	Immediate access at all times to paediatric surgery, neurosurgery and other specialties	Pediatric surgery Pediatric neurosurgery
G-BA (2021) ¹	Neurosurgery	yes/no	Pediatric neurosurgery
Knops (2012) ³	In a paediatric oncology centre, the following facilities are 24 h/day available: Paediatric intensive care unit, reachable within 10 min Extensive possibilities for imaging, like conventional X-rays, ultra sound, CT-scan/magnetic resonance imaging with the possibility for anaesthetics Anaesthetics for diagnostic procedures or therapeutic interventions Clinical chemistry laboratory Specialized haematology laboratory for morphological analysis, genotyping and immunophenotyping Transfusion medicine and laboratory Kidney dialysis		Pediatric intensive care unit Pediatric radiology Pediatric anaesthetics Laboratories Pediatric nephrology
Multidisciplinary team (MDT) and other experts			
NICE (2005) ⁷	Evidence that MDTs are established in each principal treatment centre and shared care centres		MDT established, including regularly scheduled MDT conferences
NICE (2005) ⁷	Evidence that MDTs are established in each principal treatment centre		MDT established, including regularly scheduled MDT conferences
G-BA (2021) ¹	There is close and structured cooperation within the multiprofessional team, the results of which are documented.	fulfilled/not fulfilled	MDT established, including regularly scheduled MDT conferences
DKG (2022/2021) ⁵	Presentation of multiprofessional team	Indicator target: As complete as possible presentation of the center cases in the multiprofessional team. Numerator: center cases of the denominator that	MDT established, including regularly scheduled MDT conferences

		were presented in the multiprofessional team Denominator: center cases Target: $\geq 95\%$	
Knops (2012) ³	A paediatric oncology centre has so called 'Treatment Multidisciplinary Teams' (TMDT) at its disposal for the treatment of children with cancer directed at the following tumour types: central nervous system (CNS) tumours, solid tumours (outside the CNS), retinoblastoma, lymphomas and leukaemia's (including allogenic bone marrow transplantation). The TMDTs are in charge of the care for the patient and consist of representatives of all relevant care providers.	Recommendation	MDT established, including regularly scheduled MDT conferences
Kowalczyk (2009) ⁴	The rights of the hospitalised child	A multi-disciplinary treatment team	MDT established, including regularly scheduled MDT conferences
NICE (2005) ⁷	Protocols for referral to specialist MDTs		MDT established, including regularly scheduled MDT conferences
G-BA (2021) ¹	Each patient is presented in an internal departmental meeting in the multiprofessional team and the treatment is strategically determined	yes/no	MDT established, including regularly scheduled MDT conferences
Hord (2014) ²	A regularly scheduled multidisciplinary care conference		MDT established, including regularly scheduled MDT conferences
Bradley (2013b) ⁸	Interdisciplinary Team Meetings	Indicator Rationale: Identifies the existence of regularly scheduled interdisciplinary team meetings in which nursing, medical and behavioural professionals assemble to collectively review the progress of patients and develop a comprehensive care plan addressing all needs of patients and families. Such care plans should be documented. An interdisciplinary team meeting is distinct from a tumour board. Definition: The proportion of pediatric oncology tertiary hospitals that have regularly scheduled interdisciplinary pediatric oncology team meetings to discuss patient care issues resulting in a written record. Indicator Specification: Proportion Numerator: Number of pediatric oncology tertiary	MDT established, including regularly scheduled MDT conferences

		centres that have regularly scheduled interdisciplinary pediatric oncology team meetings that produce a written record. Denominator: Number of pediatric oncology tertiary hospitals.	
NICE (2005) ⁷	Staff attendance at the MDT meetings		MDT established, including regularly scheduled MDT conferences
NICE (2005) ⁷	Adequate provision of specialist staff for every MDT		Number of pediatric oncology disciplines with multidisciplinary staffing ratios for pediatric oncology
Bradley (2013b) ⁸	Sufficient Multidisciplinary staff	<p>Indicator Rationale: Provides a measure of access to comprehensive, multidisciplinary pediatric oncology teams. Pediatric Oncology Group of Ontario (POGO)'s staffing ratio recommendations are based on the critical importance of a comprehensive, multidisciplinary team-based approach to optimal outcomes in pediatric oncology practice.</p> <p>Definition: a) Compliance with/ achievement of POGO recommended pediatric oncology discipline specific staffing ratios of patients to discipline. b) The proportion of professional pediatric oncology disciplines (for which POGO recommended multidisciplinary staffing ratios for pediatric oncology exist) for which the POGO-recommended staffing ratios have been met.</p> <p>Indicator Specifications: a) Ratios of pediatric oncology patients to the number of discipline-specific full-time equivalent (FTE) positions for each of the 10 disciplines with POGO-recommended ratios. b) Proportion</p> <p>Numerator: Number of professional pediatric oncology disciplines for which POGO-recommended multidisciplinary staffing ratios for pediatric</p>	Number of pediatric oncology disciplines with multidisciplinary staffing ratios for pediatric oncology

		<p>oncology have been met. Denominator: Number of professional pediatric oncology disciplines for which POGO-recommended multidisciplinary staffing ratios for pediatric oncology exist (i.e. 10 disciplines)</p>	
Bradley (2013a) ⁹	Sufficient multidisciplinary staff	<p>Indicator Rationale: Provides a measure of access to comprehensive, multidisciplinary pediatric oncology teams. POGO's staffing ratio recommendations are based on the critical importance of a comprehensive, multidisciplinary team-based approach to optimal outcomes in pediatric oncology practice.</p> <p>Definition: a) Compliance with/ achievement of POGOrecommended pediatric oncology discipline specific staffing ratios of patients to discipline. b) The proportion of professional pediatric oncology disciplines (for which POGOrecommended multidisciplinary staffing ratios for pediatric oncology exist) for which the POGO-recommended staffing ratios have been met.</p> <p>Indicator Specifications: a) Ratios of pediatric oncology patients to the number of discipline-specific full-time equivalent (FTE) positions for each of the 10 disciplines with POGO-recommended ratios. b) Proportion</p> <p>Numerator: Number of professional pediatric oncology disciplines for which POGO-recommended multidisciplinary staffing ratios for pediatric oncology have been met.</p> <p>Denominator: Number of professional pediatric oncology disciplines for which POGO-recommended multidisciplinary staffing ratios for pediatric oncology exist (i.e. 10 disciplines)</p>	Number of pediatric oncology disciplines with multidisciplinary staffing ratios for pediatric oncology
G-BA (2021) ¹	The multiprofessional team consists of at least the medical service, nursing service and psychosocial service and, if	fulfilled/not fulfilled	Number of pediatric oncology disciplines with multidisciplinary staffing ratios for pediatric

	necessary, the dietary/nutritional service and physiotherapy/occupational therapy		oncology Pediatric oncologists Pediatric oncology nurses Psychosocial care/services Dieticians Occupational therapists
Kowalczyk (2009) ⁴	Recommended staffing levels for the paediatric haematology/oncology ward	Staffing levels: based on the annual average activity, including bed occupancy, day ward attendees and clinics, should include: 1. a head paediatric oncologist and head nurse with appropriate deputies; 2. doctors appropriate to the figures outlined below; 3. adequate nurses to cover the workload including a link nurse who provides the link between the treating unit, parents and the local community; 4. psychology service; 5. social workers – numbers determined by patient workload; 6. ward teachers; 7. activity/play therapy; 8. physiotherapy and occupational therapy staff; 9. appropriate laboratory technicians; 10. medical secretaries and data managers; 11. rehabilitation specialists; 12. dieticians.	Number of pediatric oncology disciplines with multidisciplinary staffing ratios for pediatric oncology Pediatric oncologists Pediatric oncology nurses Psychosocial care/services Ward teachers Activity/play therapy staff Occupational therapists Laboratory technicians Medical secretaries and data managers Rehabilitation specialists Dieticians
Knops (2012) ³	A paediatric oncology centre has a functioning supportive Multidisciplinary Team at its disposal directed at the psychosocial care for paediatric oncology patients and their families. This psychosocial MDT consists at least of child psychologists, play therapists, social workers, paediatric oncology nurses, educational service workers, paediatric oncologists and if desired other specialists of the Treatment Multidisciplinary Team.	Recommendation	Number of pediatric oncology disciplines with multidisciplinary staffing ratios for pediatric oncology Psychosocial care/services Activity/play therapy staff Pediatric oncology nurses Ward teachers Pediatric oncologists
Knops (2012) ³	A paediatric oncology centre has a functioning supportive Multidisciplinary Team at its disposal directed at palliative care. This palliative care MDT consists at least of a case manager, general practitioner, district nurse, specialized paediatrician and nurse for palliative care, child psychologist and paediatric	Recommendation	Number of pediatric oncology disciplines with multidisciplinary staffing ratios for pediatric oncology Pediatric oncology nurses

	oncologist. The palliative care MDT is involved with every patient for whom cure is not feasible.		Palliative care specialists Pediatric oncologists Psychosocial care/services
Knops (2012) ³	A paediatric oncology centre has a functioning supportive Multidisciplinary Team at its disposal directed at the management of pain in children. This pain MDT consists at least of a paediatric oncologist, paediatric nurse, play therapist, paediatric neurologist and a paediatric anaesthesiologist for complex pain management.	Recommendation	Number of pediatric oncology disciplines with multidisciplinary staffing ratios for pediatric oncology Pain management experts Pediatric oncologists Pediatric oncology nurses Activity/play therapy staff Pediatric neurologist Pediatric anesthesiology
Knops (2012) ³	A treatment MDT has a logistical chain for executing and processing diagnostic biopsies. In this logistical chain the following members participate: paediatric neurosurgeon, intervention radiologist, paediatric anaesthesiologist, paediatric intensivist, paediatric pathologists and experts in the field of tumor morphology, genetics and immunology.	Recommendation	Number of pediatric oncology disciplines with multidisciplinary staffing ratios for pediatric oncology Pediatric anesthesiology Pediatric radiologists Pediatric anesthesiology Genetics specialists Pediatric critical care specialists Pediatric pathologist Facilities and Networks: Pathology Facilities and Networks: Pediatric intensive care unit
Knops (2012) ³	A paediatric oncology centre has a functioning supportive Multidisciplinary Team at its disposal directed at the follow-up care for childhood cancer survivors. This follow-up MDT consists at least of a paediatric oncologist, medical oncologist (adult care), radiotherapist, paediatric surgeon, paediatric neurosurgeon, paediatric neurologist, case manager, nurse practitioner, psychologist, education expert and employment expert.	Recommendation	Number of pediatric oncology disciplines with multidisciplinary staffing ratios for pediatric oncology Pediatric oncologists Pediatric surgeons Pediatric neurologist Pediatric oncology nurses Psychosocial care/services Ward teachers Occupational therapists

			Facilities and Networks: Neurosurgery Facilities and Networks: Radiation therapy
NICE (2005) ⁷	<p>Suggested core attendance of multidisciplinary team (MDT) members at principal treatment centres during the care pathway.</p> <p>Diagnosis Oncologist/haematologist Radiologist Surgeon/neurosurgeon Pathologist/cytogeneticist Clinical oncologist</p> <p>Treatment Treating oncologist Key worker Paediatric haematologist Specialist nurses Nurses from inpatient and day care units Specialist pharmacist Dietitian and other appropriate allied health professionals Paediatric oncology or other speciality outreach nurse/key worker</p> <p>Psychosocial support Treating oncologist and haematologist Key worker Play specialist; activity coordinator/youth worker Psychological services professional Specialist outreach nurse Appropriate allied health professionals Teacher Social worker Nurses from inpatient and day care units</p> <p>Palliative care Lead clinician Key worker</p>		<p>Number of pediatric oncology disciplines with multidisciplinary staffing ratios for pediatric oncology Pediatric oncologists Pediatric radiologists Pediatric surgeon Pediatric oncology nurses Pharmacist experienced in chemotherapy preparation Psychosocial care/services Ward teachers Activity/play therapy staff Dieticians Palliative care specialist Pediatric pathologist</p> <p>Facilities and Networks: Pediatric neurosurgery</p>

	<p>Palliative care specialist/oncologist/haematologist Social worker Specialist outreach nurse Specialist pharmacist Psychological services professional Appropriate allied health professional</p>		
Knops (2012) ³	<p>In a paediatric oncology centre, the following caregivers are present on working days between 8.00 and 18.00 o'clock, outside these hours, they are available for consultation and can be present within 60 min:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Paediatric oncologist Paediatric surgeon Paediatric neurosurgeon Paediatric intensivist Paediatric radiotherapist Paediatric neurologist Paediatric anaesthesiologist Paediatric cardiologist Paediatric nephrologist Paediatric gastroenterologist Paediatric radiologist Paediatric pulmonologist Ear–nose–throat specialist Ophthalmologist 	Recommendation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pediatric oncologist Pediatric surgeons Pediatric critical care specialists Radiation oncologists Pediatric neurologist Pediatric anesthesiology Pediatric cardiologist Pediatric nephrologist Pediatric gastroenterologist Pediatric radiologists Pediatric pulmonologist Ear–nose–throat specialist Ophthalmologist <p>Facilities and networks: Pediatric neurosurgery Facilities and networks: Intensive care unit Facilities and networks: Radiation therapy</p>
Knops (2012) ³	<p>The paediatric oncology MDT designates a practitioner-in-charge and its substitute who act on behalf of the paediatric oncology MDT. The practitioner-in-charge and its substitute are documented in the (digital) medical file and are known to the patient, parents and/or guardians.</p>		<p>Pediatric oncology practitioner-in-charge/lead clinician (also with expertise in late effects)</p>
NICE (2005) ⁷	<p>Suggested core attendance of multidisciplinary team (MDT) members responsible for the care of patients following completion of treatment.</p> <p>Late effects MDT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lead clinician (oncologist with expertise in late effects) Key worker Specialist nurse Endocrinologist 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pediatric oncology practitioner-in-charge/lead clinician (also with expertise in late effects) Pediatric oncology nurses Pediatric endocrinologist Psychosocial care/services

	Appropriate allied health professional Psychological services professional		
Hord (2014) ²	Board-certified pediatric hematologists/oncologists		Pediatric oncologists
Hord (2014) ²	Pediatric oncology nurses who are certified in chemotherapy, knowledgeable about pediatric protocols, and experienced in the management of complications of therapy; Association of Pediatric Hematology/ Oncology Nurses certification is preferable		Pediatric oncology nurses
Hord (2014) ²	Board-certified radiologists with specific expertise as evidenced by certification and training in the diagnostic imaging and radiologic intervention of infants, children, adolescents, and young adults		Pediatric radiologists
Hord (2014) ²	Board-certified surgeons with expertise in pediatric general surgery		Pediatric surgeons
Hord (2014) ²	Dentists who have completed additional training in pediatric dentistry		Dentist
Hord (2014) ²	A board-certified radiation oncologist trained and experienced in the treatment of infants, children, and adolescent		Radiation oncologists
Hord (2014) ²	Board-certified pediatric medical subspecialists available to participate actively in all areas of the care of the child with cancer, including anesthesiology, critical care, infectious diseases, cardiology, neurology, endocrinology and metabolism, genetics, gastroenterology, child and adolescent psychiatry, nephrology, palliative medicine, pulmonology, [...], and behavioral and developmental specialists		Pediatric anesthesiology Pediatric critical care specialists Pediatric infectious diseases specialists Pediatric cardiologist Pediatric neurologist Pediatric endocrinologist Genetics specialists Pediatric gastroenterologist Psychosocial care/services Pediatric nephrologist Palliative care specialists Pediatric pulmonologist
Hord (2014) ²	Pediatric physical and mental rehabilitation services, including pediatric physiatry and pediatric psychiatry		Psychosocial care/services Rehabilitation specialists
Hord (2014) ²	Experts with knowledge in complementary and alternative therapies		Complementary and alternative therapies
Hord (2014) ²	Nutrition experts with experience in pediatrics and the capability of preparing, administering, and monitoring total parenteral nutrition		Dieticians
Hord (2014) ²	Pharmacist(s) with experience and training in providing chemotherapy and supportive care medicines for pediatric		Pharmacists experienced in chemotherapy preparation

	patients with cancer; a board-certified clinical pharmacologist, where available, may be helpful in patient management		
Hord (2014) ²	Access to instruction and learning activities for hospitalized children and adolescents		Ward teachers
Hord (2014) ²	Pathologists with special expertise as evidenced by certification and training in the pathology of hematologic malignancies, tumors of the central nervous system, and solid tumors in children, adolescents, and young adults		Pediatric pathologist
Supportive care			
Supportive care: Central venous catheter (CVC)			
Olshefski (2020) ⁶	Surgical complication related to Central Venous Catheter Placement (CVC) placement	Effective communication to the surgical team regarding the intended device type is essential to ensure that the correct device is implanted. Furthermore, it is key to ensure that the central venous catheter (CVC) tip is in an acceptable location for long-term use. Failure to insert the desired device or leaving the catheter tip in an unacceptable location within the heart or great vessels counts as a Cancer Care Index event	Surgical complication rates (failure to insert the desired device or leaving the catheter tip in an unacceptable location) related to CVC placement
Bradley (2013b) ⁸	Central Venous Line (CVL) Infection Rate	Indicator Rationale: Indexes a common but potentially serious complication of use of CVLs for fluid, drug and blood product administration. CVLs are commonly used in pediatric cancer patients and infection in this patient population is particularly hazardous. Definition: The number of confirmed central venous line (CVL)-derived primary blood stream infection cases amongst pediatric oncology patients, per 1,000 pediatric oncology central venous line days. Indicator Specification: Rate Numerator: Number of confirmed CVL-derived primary blood stream infection cases amongst pediatric oncology patients with central venous lines over 12-month period, multiplied by 1,000. Denominator: Number of pediatric oncology CVL days over the same 12-month period	Complication rates: particularly the incidence of CVC-associated infection
NICE (2005) ⁷	Complication rates, particularly incidence of (central venous catheter) CVC-associated infection		Complication rates: particularly the incidence of CVC-associated infection
Supportive care: CVC and supportive care (guidelines) and febrile neutropenia (F&N)			

Bradley (2013b) ⁸	Supportive care guidelines	Existence of supportive care guidelines Written policies/ procedures for the management of CVC	Existence of supportive care guidelines Written policies/ procedures for the management of CVC Guidelines on how to approach a child with F&N (availability, risk-stratified approach, escalation for fever persistence)
Bradley (2013a) ⁹	Supportive care guidelines	<p>Indicator Rationale: Provides a baseline measure of whether formal policies are in place for management of four key supportive care issues in pediatric oncology. As primary treatment modalities have intensified, so too has the need for formalized supportive care guidelines. Inconsistent and variable supportive care can add substantially to the burden of illness.</p> <p>Definition: The proportion of pediatric oncology tertiary and/or Satellite programs that have formal, written policies/ procedures for the management of: a) fever/ neutropenia (in both tertiary and Satellite centres); b) ambulatory management of fever/ neutropenia (in the tertiary centres only); c) central venous line management (in both tertiary and Satellite centres); d) anti-neoplastic induced nausea and vomiting (in both tertiary and Satellite centres)</p> <p>Indicator Specification: Proportion Numerator: Number of tertiary and/ or Satellite pediatric oncology programs who have formal supportive care guidelines for the management of each of the above four supportive care issues for children with cancer. Denominator: Number of tertiary and/ or Satellite pediatric oncology programs.</p>	Existence of supportive care guidelines Written policies/ procedures for the management of CVC Guidelines on how to approach a child with F&N (availability, risk-stratified approach, escalation for fever persistence)
Supportive care: Supportive care (guidelines)			
Knops (2012) ³	A paediatric oncology centre has written guidelines about diagnostics and treatment of all paediatric cancer types,	Recommendation	Existence of supportive care guidelines Supportive care (guidelines for):

	supportive care (including pain management), follow-up care after the end of treatment and palliative care.		Pain relief, including local protocol for pain relief procedures and adequate pain management Supportive care (guidelines) for: Palliative care (including bereavement)
NICE (2005) ⁷	Written protocol in management of nausea, vomiting and bowel disturbance in use with evidence of multidisciplinary input and regular review		Supportive care (guidelines for): nausea, vomiting and bowel disturbance
NICE (2005) ⁷	Compliance with and effectiveness of protocol (Management of nausea, vomiting and bowel disturbance)		Supportive care (guidelines for): nausea, vomiting and bowel disturbance
Olshefski (2020) ⁶	Nutritional assessment	Detailed survey of the patient's nutritional status by a nutritional expert [...] should be performed before initiating a therapy, which provides a baseline to manage nutrition throughout treatment. Not documenting this assessment constitutes an event	Supportive care (guidelines for): Nutritional assessment
Bradley (2013b) ⁸	Guidelines for Nutritional Support	Indicator Rationale: Proposed as a high-level indicator of best practice regarding nutritional support for children with cancer. Appropriate nutritional support influences outcome and quality of life for pediatric cancer patients. Definition: The proportion of pediatric oncology tertiary centres that utilize a standardized guideline for nutritional support for pediatric oncology patients. Indicator Specification: Proportion Numerator: Number of pediatric oncology tertiary programs in Ontario that utilize a standardized guideline for nutritional support of pediatric cancer patients. Denominator: Number of pediatric oncology tertiary centres in Ontario.	Supportive care (guidelines for): Nutritional assessment
NICE (2005) ⁷	Provision of protocols detailing measures to ensure adequate nutritional support		Supportive care (guidelines for): Nutritional assessment
NICE (2005) ⁷	Nutritional status of patients		Supportive care (guidelines for): Nutritional assessment
Knops (2012) ³	The caregiver makes assistance in nutrition, also for the home-situation, available.	Recommendation	Supportive care (guidelines for): Nutritional assessment

NICE (2005) ⁷	Evidence that there are effective dental screening and treatment protocols available before and during treatment		Supportive care (guidelines for): Dental care
NICE (2005) ⁷	Palliative Care		Supportive care (guidelines for): Palliative care (including bereavement)
Kowalczyk (2009) ⁴	Palliative Care		Supportive care (guidelines for): Palliative care (including bereavement)
Olshefski (2020) ⁶	Palliative care consult	...in patients with progressive cancer, the goal is to provide palliative care options at least 30 days before death; if palliative care or hospice referral, including a face-to-face consultation, was not initiated within that time frame, it becomes a Cancer Care Index event; as with influenza vaccine administration, if a family refuses a consultation with a palliative care physician, it is counted as an event because..., it is the responsibility of the oncologist to make the case for palliative care when appropriate	Supportive care (guidelines for): Palliative care (including bereavement)
de Rojas (2019) ¹⁰	% of relapsed patients receiving support from the local Palliative Care Unit		Supportive care (guidelines for): Palliative care (including bereavement)
Bradley (2013b) ⁸	Patients Referred for End-of-Life Interlink Care	Indicator Rationale: Provides an index of the coordination of hospital and community-based resources to effect optimal end-of-life care. Definition: The proportion of pediatric oncology patients, 0 to 17 years of age, who are referred to the Interlink nursing service for end-of-life care. Indicator Specification: Proportion Numerator: Number of pediatric oncology patients, 0 to 17 years of age, who are referred to Interlink at the time of end-of-life care. Denominator: Number of pediatric oncology patients, 0 to 17 years of age, who die.	Supportive care (guidelines for): Palliative care (including bereavement)
Knops (2012) ³	The physician-in-charge and the case manager of palliative care make a palliative care scheme based on values, goals, needs and developmental stage of the patient and its family, in accordance with law.	Recommendation	Supportive care (guidelines for): Palliative care (including bereavement)

Knops (2012) ³	The caregiver emphasizes that optimal palliative care will be given when cure is no longer feasible.	Recommendation	Supportive care (guidelines for): Palliative care (including bereavement)
Knops (2012) ³	The caregiver provides for the family of deceased children a program for dealing with bereavement.	Recommendation	Supportive care (guidelines for): Palliative care (including bereavement)
NICE (2005) ⁷	Bereavement		Supportive care (guidelines for): Palliative care (including bereavement)
NICE (2005) ⁷	Rehabilitation		Supportive care (guidelines for): (Neuro-) Rehabilitation
Kowalczyk (2009) ⁴	Rehabilitation		Supportive care (guidelines for): (Neuro-) Rehabilitation
NICE (2005) ⁷	Documented referral policies to guide referral for rehabilitation		Supportive care (guidelines for): (Neuro-) Rehabilitation
NICE (2014) ¹¹	Structure: Evidence of local arrangements to ensure that all children [...] who have had a central nervous system malignancy receive a specialist neuro-rehabilitation care package.		Supportive care (guidelines for): (Neuro-) Rehabilitation
NICE (2014) ¹¹	Process: The proportion of children [...] who have had treatment for a central nervous system malignancy who receive a specialist neuro-rehabilitation care package.	Numerator – the number of people in the denominator receiving a specialist neuro-rehabilitation care package. Denominator – the number of children [...] who have had treatment for a central nervous system malignancy.	Supportive care (guidelines for): (Neuro-) Rehabilitation
NICE (2014) ¹¹	Process: The proportion of children [...] with cancer who are assessed for potential future fertility problems and advised about their options for fertility preservation before treatment is started.	Numerator – the number of people in the denominator who are assessed for potential future fertility problems before treatment and are advised about their options for fertility preservation. Denominator – the number of children [...] diagnosed with cancer.	Supportive care (guidelines for): Fertility (preservation) discussion
NICE (2014) ¹¹	Structure: Evidence of local arrangements to ensure that children [...] with cancer are assessed for potential future fertility problems and advised about their options for fertility preservation before treatment is started.		Supportive care (guidelines for): Fertility (preservation) discussion
Knops (2012) ³	The caregiver actively offers the possibility of fertility preservation to boys as well as girls.	Recommendation	Supportive care (guidelines for): Fertility (preservation) discussion

Olshefski (2020) ⁶	Fertility discussion	Discussing implications of recommended treatment regarding fertility is required in the consent discussion and must be documented in the electronic medical record, or it counts as a Cancer Care Index event	Supportive care (guidelines for): Fertility (preservation) discussion
NICE (2005) ⁷	Written protocols for pain relief procedures		Supportive care (guidelines for): Pain relief, including local protocol for pain relief procedures and adequate pain management
NICE (2005) ⁷	Evidence that specialist and age-appropriate pain relief services are available when required		Supportive care (guidelines for): Pain relief, including local protocol for pain relief procedures and adequate pain management
Teichman (2017) ¹²	Pain management	Population: all patients Outcome: mean/median score on survey question, "how frequently did your health care provider ask you about the pain your child was experiencing?" Respondents choose from 4 options (never/rarely/at most visits/at every visit). Measurement: 6-mo audit of all surveys. Responses converted to a 1-4 scale	Supportive care (guidelines for): Pain relief, including local protocol for pain relief procedures and adequate pain management
IQWiG (2005) ¹³	Pain	(can be benchmarked)	Supportive care (guidelines for): Pain relief, including local protocol for pain relief procedures and adequate pain management
Bradley (2013b) ⁸	Access to Expert Management of Pain Control	Indicator Rationale: Measures access to expert pain management, or pain teams, for the control of acute or chronic pain in children with cancer at the tertiary pediatric oncology program level. Pain in children with cancer can be a frequent occurrence and difficult to control and therefore may require specialized expertise through access to comprehensive pain management care services. Definition: The proportion of pediatric oncology programs that have access to expert pain management, defined as a formal, consistent resource group or expert staff member for consultation and/or management of acute or	Supportive care (guidelines for): Pain relief, including local protocol for pain relief procedures and adequate pain management

		<p>chronic pain for children with cancer. Indicator Specification: Proportion Numerator: Number of hospital survey respondents in the tertiary pediatric oncology programs who have access to a formal, consistent expert resource group or staff member for consultation and/ or management of acute or chronic pain for children with cancer. Denominator: Number of survey respondents in the tertiary pediatric oncology programs</p>	
Bradley (2013a) ⁹	Access to expert pain management	<p>Indicator Rationale: Measures access to expert pain management, or pain teams, for the control of acute or chronic pain in children with cancer at the tertiary pediatric oncology program level. Pain in children with cancer can be a frequent occurrence and difficult to control and therefore may require specialized expertise through access to comprehensive pain management care services. Definition: The proportion of pediatric oncology programs that have access to expert pain management, defined as a formal, consistent resource group or expert staff member for consultation and/or management of acute or chronic pain for children with cancer. Indicator Specification: Proportion Numerator: Number of hospital survey respondents in the tertiary pediatric oncology programs who have access to a formal, consistent expert resource group or staff member for consultation and/ or management of acute or chronic pain for children with cancer. Denominator: Number of survey respondents in the tertiary pediatric oncology programs</p>	Supportive care (guidelines for): Pain relief, including local protocol for pain relief procedures and adequate pain management
IQWiG (2005) ¹³	Procedures for psychosocial support and rehabilitation		Supportive care (guidelines for): Psychological or psychosocial care, including provision of/information about social care
NICE (2005) ⁷	Psychosocial care		Supportive care (guidelines for): Psychological or psychosocial

			care, including provision of/information about social care
NICE (2014) ¹¹	Structure: b) Evidence of local arrangements to ensure that children [...] with cancer, and their families and carers, can access services delivering psychological and social support		Supportive care (guidelines for): Psychological or psychosocial care, including provision of/information about social care
G-BA (2021) ¹	It (psychosocial service) consists of employees of the: - psychological-psychotherapeutic area	fulfilled/not fulfilled	Supportive care (guidelines for): Psychological or psychosocial care, including provision of/information about social care
DKG (2022/2021) ⁵	Counseling by the Psychosocial Service (PSD)	Indicator target: As complete as possible counseling of patients and families by the psychosocial service. Numerator: Center cases of the denominator or their families who have been counselled by the psychosocial service. Denominator: center cases Target: $\geq 95\%$	Supportive care (guidelines for): Psychological or psychosocial care, including provision of/information about social care
Kowalczyk (2009) ⁴	Psychological and psychosocial care		Supportive care (guidelines for): Psychological or psychosocial care, including provision of/information about social care
Olshefski (2020) ⁶	Psychology referral	Each patient should be referred to psychology and social work and an education specialist, when age appropriate, who performs a needs assessment; If referral in any of these areas does not occur, it becomes a Cancer Care Index event	Supportive care (guidelines for): Psychological or psychosocial care, including provision of/information about social care
Knops (2012) ³	The caregiver provides specialized psychosocial and (neuro-)psychological care depending on the nature of the problems.	Recommendation	Supportive care (guidelines for): Psychological or psychosocial care, including provision of/information about social care
G-BA (2021) ¹	It (psychosocial service) consists of employees of the: - and the socio-pedagogical-social work area	fulfilled/not fulfilled	Supportive care (guidelines for): Psychological or psychosocial care, including provision of/information about social care
Kowalczyk (2009) ⁴	Social care		Supportive care (guidelines for): Psychological or psychosocial care, including provision of/information about social care

Olshefski (2020) ⁶	Social work referral	Each patient should be referred to psychology and social work and an education specialist, when age appropriate, who performs a needs assessment; If referral in any of these areas does not occur, it becomes a Cancer Care Index event	Supportive care (guidelines for): Psychological or psychosocial care, including provision of/information about social care
Kowalczyk (2009) ⁴	The rights of the hospitalised child	Play and education facilities	Supportive care (guidelines for): Provision of school education
Kowalczyk (2009) ⁴	Education		Supportive care (guidelines for): Provision of school education
Olshefski (2020) ⁶	Education needs assessments	Each patient should be referred to psychology and social work and an education specialist, when age appropriate, who performs a needs assessment; If referral in any of these areas does not occur, it becomes a Cancer Care Index event	Supportive care (guidelines for): Provision of school education
Knops (2012) ³	A paediatric oncology centre provides educational services during all stages of care	Recommendation	Supportive care (guidelines for): Provision of cancer education
Hord (2014) ²	A formal program for cancer education for the patient, family, and or caregiver and instruction on self-management		Supportive care (guidelines for): Provision of cancer education
Supportive care: Febrile neutropenia (F&N)			
NICE (2005) ⁷	Development of national guidelines on febrile neutropenia		Guidelines on how to approach a child with F&N (availability, risk-stratified approach, escalation for fever persistence)
NICE (2005) ⁷	Development of risk-stratified protocols for the management of febrile neutropenia		Guidelines on how to approach a child with F&N (availability, risk-stratified approach, escalation for fever persistence)
NICE (2005) ⁷	Development of protocols for outpatient treatment of febrile neutropenia		Guidelines on how to approach a child with F&N (availability, risk-stratified approach, escalation for fever persistence)
NICE (2005) ⁷	Compliance with protocols and guidelines (febrile neutropenia)		Guidelines on how to approach a child with F&N (availability, risk-stratified approach, escalation for fever persistence)
ten Berg (2018) ¹⁴	Having a general recommendation on the antimicrobial policy of febrile neutropenia in children with cancer 1. No recommendation 2. Verbal agreement 3. Written recommendation in own document system		Guidelines on how to approach a child with F&N (availability, risk-stratified approach, escalation for fever persistence)

	4. According to the Dutch Childhood Oncology Group (DCOG) guideline		
ten Berg (2018) ¹⁴	Percentage of febrile neutropenia episodes without microbial focus, which are treated with ceftazidim	Numerator: The number of febrile neutropenia episodes without microbial focus, for which patients received ceftazidim according to the Dutch Childhood Oncology Group (DCOG) guideline Denominator: All episodes of febrile neutropenia without microbial focus	Number/Proportion of clinical F&N episodes in which the patients with or without microbial focus are treated with first line antibiotics according to local guidelines
ten Berg (2018) ¹⁴	The percentage of clinical febrile neutropenia episodes in children with cancer, in which a patient is admitted to the intensive care unit (ICU)	Numerator: The number of clinical febrile neutropenia episodes in children with cancer, in which a patient is admitted to the ICU Denominator: All clinical febrile neutropenia episodes	Number/Proportion of clinical F&N episodes in which patients are admitted to ICU
ten Berg (2018) ¹⁴	The percentage of clinical febrile neutropenia episodes of which patients have died	Numerator: The number of clinical febrile neutropenia episodes of which patients have died Denominator: The total number of clinical febrile neutropenia episodes	Number/Proportion of clinical F&N episodes in which the patient died
Olshefski (2020) ⁶	Fungal Health Care-Associated Infections (HAI)	...infections are tracked and included in the Cancer Care Index if hospital acquired	Fungal Health Care-Associated Infections (HAI)
Fletcher (2013) ¹⁵	Time to antibiotics (TTA) of 60 minutes	...we propose 60 minutes as the TTA benchmark for pediatric patients with febrile neutropenia TTA: defined as the time in minutes from presentation to either triage (emergency department [ED]), registration (outpatient clinic), or admitting (direct admission) to the first dose of parenteral antibiotics. Measured in 60-minute intervals and as continuous variable	Time to antibiotic (TTA) administration
McCavit & Winick (2012) ¹⁶	Time-to-Antibiotic Administration (TTA)	Abstract: Nearly half of respondents track TTA. Most reported using a benchmark of less than 60 min from arrival. TTA is a commonly used quality-of-care measure for pediatric febrile neutropenia despite an absence of studies establishing its validity and a lack of data supporting its impact on outcomes of febrile neutropenia. ...as the time required for the administration of the first dose of empiric antibiotics in children with febrile neutropenia. It was implied that the TTA measurement began upon the patient's arrival at	Time to antibiotic (TTA) administration

		<p>the institution, but this was not explicitly stated.</p> <p>...as a Quality of Care Measure in Children With Febrile Neutropenia most clinics using it as a quality measure set <60 min as a threshold</p> <p>Results: Forty-five percent [...] of respondents reported tracking TTA as a quality-of-care measure [...]. Of those, over 90% reported using a TTA standard/benchmark of <30 or <60 min and use the same TTA standard/benchmark for the outpatient clinic, the ED, and the inpatient unit.</p> <p>But: ...further investigation of its validity as a measure of the process and outcomes of care are warranted before it is accepted as a standard quality-of-care measure in the pediatric oncology community</p>	
Olshefski (2020) ⁶	Time to Antibiotics for fever/neutropenia	best practice requires prompt antibiotic administration to febrile patients with neutropenia - within 60 minutes after emergency department or hospital arrival, rather than from the time when the absolute neutrophil count is determined if that time exceeds 60 minutes, it counts as a Cancer Care Index event	Time to antibiotic (TTA) administration
Corey & Snyder (2008) ¹⁷	Time to antibiotics 30-minute door/fever-to-patient delivery (30-minute door/fever-to-patient antibiotics delivery)	...a goal of 30 minutes was chosen for the initiation of STAT antibiotics to a febrile neutropenic patient admission or new-onset fever and was to be achieved at a rate of 95%	Time to antibiotic (TTA) administration
Treatment			
NICE (2005) ⁷	Rates of refusal and failure to complete treatment – annual report		Number/Proportion of refusal and failure to complete treatment
NICE (2005) ⁷	Compliance with chemotherapy protocols		Protocol compliance (e.g., number of major clinical trial protocol violations)

NICE (2005) ⁷	Protocol compliance by both patients and clinical specialists		Protocol compliance (e.g., number of major clinical trial protocol violations)
Bradley (2013b) ⁸	Major Clinical Trial Protocol Violation	Indicator Rationale: Provides an externally assessed standardized measure of compliance with clinical trial specification and good clinical practice. Definition: The proportion of patients on Children's Oncology Group (COG) or Dana Farber Cancer Institute (DFCI) clinical trials who have a documented major clinical trial protocol violation, such as an error in timing of a step in treatment or investigation Indicator Specification: Proportion Numerator: Number of COG or DFCI major clinical trial protocol violations. Denominator: Number of pediatric cancer patients enrolled on COG or DFCI clinical trials.	Protocol compliance (e.g., number of major clinical trial protocol violations)
de Rojas (2019) ¹⁰	Chemotherapy (CT) plan deviations		Protocol compliance (e.g., number of major clinical trial protocol violations)
NICE (2014) ¹¹	Structure: Evidence of local arrangements to ensure that children [...] are assessed for eligibility for relevant clinical trials and offered the opportunity to take part.		Number/Proportion of clinical trial participation
NICE (2014) ¹¹	Process: a) The proportion of children [...] with cancer and eligible for a clinical trial who are offered the opportunity to take part.	Numerator – the number of people in the denominator offered the opportunity to take part. Denominator – children [...] with cancer and eligible for a clinical trial.	Number/Proportion of clinical trial participation
Knops (2012) ³	The physician-in-charge offers to children, who are eligible, participation in clinical trials. If children do not participate in a clinical trial and if there is no (inter)national guideline available, an individual treatment scheme will be developed based on maximal scientific proof and expertise.	Recommendation	Number/Proportion of clinical trial participation
NICE (2014) ¹¹	Process: b) The proportion of children [...] with cancer who are recruited	Numerator – the number of people in the denominator recruited into the clinical trial. Denominator – the number of children [...] with cancer and eligible for a clinical trial.	Number/Proportion of clinical trial participation

DKG (2022/2021) ⁵	Included center cases in therapy optimization studies/German Society for Pediatric Oncology and Hematology (GPOH) registries.	Indicator target: As complete as possible inclusion of center cases in therapy optimization studies/GPOH registries. Numerator: center cases included in therapy optimization studies/GPOH registries. Denominator: primary cases with national residence. Target: $\geq 90\%$	Number/Proportion of clinical trial participation
NICE (2005) ⁷	Surveys of numbers of children and young people who are entered into available clinical trials		Number/Proportion of clinical trial participation
Bradley (2013a) ⁹	Clinical trial participation	Indicator Rationale: This indicator indexes the extent to which Ontario's treatment centres are aligned with what is universally accepted as the gold standard of care, recognizing that there may be many reasons for non-participation in a clinical trial. Comparison to similar indicators in American and European groups will provide a benchmark. Definition: The proportion of newly diagnosed pediatric cancer cases, 0 to 17 years of age inclusive, diagnosed and treated in a pediatric cancer centre in Ontario, who are enrolled on a Research Ethics Board (REB) approved, cancer therapeutic clinical trial. Excludes enrolments on biology, registry, or observational studies. Indicator Specification: Proportion. Numerator: Total number of newly diagnosed pediatric oncology cases, 0 to 17 years of age inclusive, diagnosed and treated at a pediatric cancer centre in Ontario, who are enrolled on a REB-approved, cancer therapeutic clinical trial. Denominator: Total number of newly diagnosed pediatric oncology cases, 0 to 17 years of age, diagnosed and treated at a pediatric cancer centre in Ontario.	Number/Proportion of clinical trial participation
de Rojas (2019) ¹⁰	% of patients enrolled in clinical trials as salvage treatment		Number/Proportion of clinical trial participation
Bradley (2013b) ⁸	Clinical Trial Participation	Indicator Rationale: This indicator indexes the extent to which Ontario's treatment centres are	Number/Proportion of clinical trial participation

		<p>aligned with what is universally accepted as the gold standard of care, recognizing that there may be many reasons for non-participation in a clinical trial. Comparison to similar indicators in American and European groups will provide a benchmark.</p> <p>Definition: The proportion of newly diagnosed pediatric cancer cases, 0 to 17 years of age inclusive, diagnosed and treated in a pediatric cancer centre in Ontario, who are enrolled on a Research Ethics Board (REB) approved, cancer therapeutic clinical trial.</p> <p>Excludes enrolments on biology, registry, or observational studies.</p> <p>Indicator Specification: Proportion.</p> <p>Numerator: Total number of newly diagnosed pediatric oncology cases, 0 to 17 years of age inclusive, diagnosed and treated at a pediatric cancer centre in Ontario, who are enrolled on a REB-approved, cancer therapeutic clinical trial.</p> <p>Denominator: Total number of newly diagnosed pediatric oncology cases, 0 to 17 years of age, diagnosed and treated at a pediatric cancer centre in Ontario.</p>	
de Rojas (2019) ¹⁰	% of patients enrolled in clinical trials as frontline treatment		Number/Proportion of clinical trial participation
DKG (2022/2021) ⁵	Therapy deviation from tumor conference recommendation	<p>Target: Deviation from the recommendation of the tumor conference as seldom as possible.</p> <p>Numerator: Center cases of the denominator in which there was at least one deviation from the therapy recommendation(s) of the tumor conference.</p> <p>Denominator: center cases that were presented at the interdisciplinary tumor conference</p> <p>Target ≤ 5%</p>	Number/Proportion of patients presented in the interdisciplinary tumor conference (for solid and liquid tumors separately or combined)
G-BA (2021) ¹	If the patient needs to be cared for by several disciplines, he or she will also be presented in an interdisciplinary tumor conference	yes/no	Number/Proportion of patients presented in the interdisciplinary tumor conference (for solid and liquid tumors separately or combined)

G-BA (2021) ¹	The result of the interdisciplinary tumor conference is documented	yes/no	Number/Proportion of patients presented in the interdisciplinary tumor conference (for solid and liquid tumors separately or combined)
Hord (2014) ²	A regularly scheduled multidisciplinary pediatric tumor board		Number/Proportion of patients presented in the interdisciplinary tumor conference (for solid and liquid tumors separately or combined)
Bradley (2013b) ⁸	Tumour Boards	<p>Indicator Rationale: This indicator will measure the availability of regularly scheduled tumour boards. A tumour board is a multidisciplinary treatmentplanning forum in which a number of physicians who are experts in different specialties review and discuss the medical condition and treatment options of a patient. A tumour board review may include the expert input of a pediatric oncologist, a surgeon, a pathologist, a diagnostic imaging specialist and a radiation oncologist. The main purpose of the tumour board is to ensure that all appropriate diagnostic tests, treatment options, and the most appropriate treatment recommendations are generated for each cancer patient. The discussions of the tumor board should be recorded.</p> <p>Definition: The proportion of pediatric oncology tertiary hospitals that have regularly scheduled multidisciplinary pediatric oncology tumour boards that produce a written record.</p> <p>Indicator Specification: Proportion</p> <p>Numerator: Number of pediatric oncology tertiary hospitals that have regularly scheduled multidisciplinary pediatric oncology tumour boards that produce a written record.</p> <p>Denominator: Number of pediatric oncology tertiary hospitals.</p>	Number/Proportion of patients presented in the interdisciplinary tumor conference (for solid and liquid tumors separately or combined)
DKG (2022/2021) ⁵	Presentation of interdisciplinary tumor conference	Indicator target: As complete as possible presentation of center cases (main group II-XII) in the interdisciplinary tumor conference.	Number/Proportion of patients presented in the interdisciplinary tumor conference (for solid and

		Numerator: center cases of the denominator that were presented in the interdisciplinary tumor conference Denominator: center cases main group II-XII (without main group I). Target $\geq 95\%$	liquid tumors separately or combined)
Treatment: Delay in/ Wait time to start of			
NICE (2005) ⁷	Delays to start of radiotherapy		Delay in/ Wait time to start of Radiotherapy
Bradley (2013b) ⁸	Chemotherapy Admission Delay	Indicator Rationale: This indicator will index the frequency with which chemotherapy administration has to be deferred for resource reasons, measured over a specified and reasonable time frame. No absolute benchmark exists, but the presumption that a delay of greater than 72 hours is not acceptable accords with clinical trial protocol specifications. Definition: The proportion of admissions for chemotherapy that are delayed for greater than 72 hours from the time the patient is deemed ready for admission, due to a lack of hospital bed (i.e. hospital resource) availability. Indicator Specification: Proportion Numerator: Number of pediatric oncology admissions for chemotherapy that are delayed for greater than 72 hours from the time the patient is deemed ready for admission. Denominator: Number of pediatric oncology admissions for chemotherapy.	Delay in/ Wait time to start of: Chemotherapy
Bradley (2013a) ⁹	Chemotherapy admission delay	Indicator Rationale: This indicator will index the frequency with which chemotherapy administration has to be deferred for resource reasons, measured over a specified and reasonable time frame. No absolute benchmark exists, but the presumption that a delay of greater than 72 hours is not acceptable accords with clinical trial protocol specifications. Definition: The proportion of admissions for	Delay in/ Wait time to start of: Chemotherapy

		<p>chemotherapy that are delayed for greater than 72 hours from the time the patient is deemed ready for admission, due to a lack of hospital bed (i.e. hospital resource) availability.</p> <p>Indicator Specification: Proportion</p> <p>Numerator: Number of pediatric oncology admissions for chemotherapy that are delayed for greater than 72 hours from the time the patient is deemed ready for admission.</p> <p>Denominator: Number of pediatric oncology admissions for chemotherapy.</p>	
NICE (2005) ⁷	Delays to start of planned chemotherapy		Delay in/ Wait time to start of: Chemotherapy
Bradley (2013b) ⁸	First Therapeutic Intervention Wait Time	<p>Indicator Rationale: Provides a measure of efficacy of implementation of treatment following a definitive diagnosis and will allow comparison between Provincial values and individual tertiary centres. If differences exist, they may provide evidence and support requests for incremental resource support.</p> <p>Definition: The number of days between the date of diagnosis and the date of first therapeutic intervention. The date of diagnosis is the date on which the definitive procedure confirming the diagnosis was carried out.</p> <p>The date of first therapeutic intervention is the date on which the first therapeutic intervention (i.e. chemotherapy, radiotherapy, or surgery) was initiated.</p> <p>Indicator Specification: Median, Range, and 90th percentile</p>	Delay in/ Wait time to start of: First therapeutic intervention
Bradley (2013a) ⁹	First therapeutic intervention wait time	<p>Indicator Rationale: Provides a measure of efficacy of implementation of treatment following a definitive diagnosis and will allow comparison between Provincial values and individual tertiary centres. If differences exist, they may provide evidence and support requests for incremental resource support.</p> <p>Definition: The number of days between the date of diagnosis and the date of first therapeutic intervention. The date of diagnosis is the date on which the definitive procedure confirming the</p>	Delay in/ Wait time to start of: First therapeutic intervention

		<p>diagnosis was carried out. The date of first therapeutic intervention is the date on which the first therapeutic intervention (i.e. chemotherapy, radiotherapy, or surgery) was initiated. Indicator Specification: Median, Range, and 90th percentile</p>	
NICE (2005) ⁷	Time taken for the production of pathology reports		Delay in/ Wait time to start of release of pathology results
Bradley (2013b) ⁸	Time Taken for the Production of Pathology Reports	<p>Indicator Rationale: This indicator will measure the turnaround time within the diagnostic labs to enable the start of appropriate therapy. It will allow comparison to a benchmark Definition: The number of days between the date that a definitive diagnostic specimen is received by the pathology department to the date a definitive pathology report is issued. Indicator Specification: Mean, Median, Interquartile Range</p>	Delay in/ Wait time to start of release of pathology results
Bradley (2013a) ⁹	Time to pathology report production	<p>Indicator Rationale: This indicator will measure the turnaround time within the diagnostic labs to enable the start of appropriate therapy. It will allow comparison to a benchmark Definition: The number of days between the date that a definitive diagnostic specimen is received by the pathology department to the date a definitive pathology report is issued. Indicator Specification: Mean, Median, Interquartile Range</p>	Delay in/ Wait time to start of release of pathology results
Treatment: Medication			
NICE (2014) ¹¹	Outcome: The number of patient safety incidents in children [...] related to chemotherapy prescriptions.		Number/Proportion of patient safety incidents related to chemotherapy prescriptions
Bradley (2013b) ⁸	Actual Drug/ Dose Errors	<p>Indicator Rationale: Pediatric oncology patients on active therapy are prescribed a range of medications including drugs with significant toxicity and narrow therapeutic margins. This indicator will provide an index of the frequency with which actual medication errors occur (i.e. the incorrect drug or dose is administered to the patient).</p>	Number/Proportion of actual drug or dose errors identified for patients on active treatment

		<p>Definition: The number of actual drug or dose errors identified for pediatric oncology patients on active treatment.</p> <p>Indicator Specification: Proportion</p> <p>Numerator: Number of actual drug or dose errors that were identified for pediatric oncology patients on active treatment.</p> <p>Denominator: Number of pediatric oncology patients on active treatment.</p>	
Bradley (2013a) ⁹	Actual drug/dose errors	<p>Indicator Rationale: Pediatric oncology patients on active therapy are prescribed a range of medications including drugs with significant toxicity and narrow therapeutic margins. This indicator will provide an index of the frequency with which actual medication errors occur (i.e. the incorrect drug or dose is administered to the patient).</p> <p>Definition: The number of actual drug or dose errors identified for pediatric oncology patients on active treatment.</p> <p>Indicator Specification: Proportion</p> <p>Numerator: Number of actual drug or dose errors that were identified for pediatric oncology patients on active treatment.</p> <p>Denominator: Number of pediatric oncology patients on active treatment.</p>	Number/Proportion of actual drug or dose errors identified for patients on active treatment
NICE (2005) ⁷	Errors and near misses		Number/Proportion of actual drug or dose errors identified for patients on active treatment
NICE (2005) ⁷	Incident reporting of errors and near misses		Number/Proportion of actual drug or dose errors identified for patients on active treatment
Bradley (2013a) ⁹	Potential drug/dose errors	<p>Indicator Rationale: Pediatric oncology patients on active therapy are prescribed a range of medications including drugs with significant toxicity and narrow therapeutic margins. This indicator will provide an index of the frequency with which potential medication errors occur (i.e. the error is detected before being administered to the patient).</p> <p>Definition: The number of potential drug or dose errors (i.e. near misses) that were identified prior to</p>	Number/Proportion of potential drug or dose errors identified for patients on active treatment

		administration in pediatric oncology patients on active treatment. Indicator Specification: Proportion Numerator: Number of potential drug or dose errors that were identified prior to administration for pediatric oncology patients on active treatment. Denominator: Number of pediatric oncology patients on active treatment.	
Bradley (2013b) ⁸	Potential Drug/ Dose Errors (Near Misses)	Indicator Rationale: Pediatric oncology patients on active therapy are prescribed a range of medications including drugs with significant toxicity and narrow therapeutic margins. This indicator will provide an index of the frequency with which potential medication errors occur (i.e. the error is detected before being administered to the patient). Definition: The number of potential drug or dose errors (i.e. near misses) that were identified prior to administration in pediatric oncology patients on active treatment. Indicator Specification: Proportion Numerator: Number of potential drug or dose errors that were identified prior to administration for pediatric oncology patients on active treatment. Denominator: Number of pediatric oncology patients on active treatment.	Number/Proportion of potential drug or dose errors identified for patients on active treatment
NICE (2005) ⁷	Prescribing errors		Number/Proportion of potential drug or dose errors identified for patients on active treatment
Bradley (2013a) ⁹	Wait time: Sedation for ambulatory procedures	Indicator Rationale: The lack of timely access to anesthesia services can delay diagnostic procedures, surgical interventions, radiation delivery, and routine intrathecal chemotherapy. This indicator will index the frequency with which non-emergent, ambulatory pediatric oncology procedures requiring anesthesia are deferred until the next day or beyond due to lack of availability of anesthesia services. Deferral of ambulatory procedures until the next day or beyond places an	Number/Proportion of elective pediatric oncology ambulatory procedures requiring anesthesia that are deferred to the next day or beyond due to resource limitation(s)

		<p>additional burden on patients and families as another visit to the hospital is required.</p> <p>Definition: The proportion of elective pediatric oncology ambulatory procedures requiring anesthesia deferred to the next day or beyond due to hospital resource limitation(s).</p> <p>Indicator Specification: Proportion Numerator: Number of elective pediatric oncology ambulatory procedures requiring anesthesia that are deferred to the next day or beyond due to resource limitation(s). Denominator: Number of elective pediatric oncology ambulatory procedures requiring anesthesia.</p>	
Bradley (2013b) ⁸	Wait Time for Ambulatory Procedures Requiring Sedation	<p>Indicator Rationale: The lack of timely access to anesthesia services can delay diagnostic procedures, surgical interventions, radiation delivery, and routine intrathecal chemotherapy. This indicator will index the frequency with which non-emergent, ambulatory pediatric oncology procedures requiring anesthesia are deferred until the next day or beyond due to lack of availability of anesthesia services. Deferral of ambulatory procedures until the next day or beyond places an additional burden on patients and families as another visit to the hospital is required.</p> <p>Definition: The proportion of elective pediatric oncology ambulatory procedures requiring anesthesia deferred to the next day or beyond due to hospital resource limitation(s).</p> <p>Indicator Specification: Proportion Numerator: Number of elective pediatric oncology ambulatory procedures requiring anesthesia that are deferred to the next day or beyond due to</p>	Number/Proportion of elective pediatric oncology ambulatory procedures requiring anesthesia that are deferred to the next day or beyond due to resource limitation(s)

		resource limitation(s). Denominator: Number of elective pediatric oncology ambulatory procedures requiring anesthesia.	
Long-term care			
Kowalczyk (2009) ⁴	Requirements of a Paediatric Haematology and/or Oncology Unit	There should be systems in place once treatment has finished in order to monitor long-term outcomes.	Established follow-up structure
Kowalczyk (2009) ⁴	Monitoring the late outcomes of cancer		Established follow-up structure
NICE(2005) ⁷	Appropriate follow-up of patients at risk of late effects		Established follow-up structure
NICE (2005) ⁷	Documented local protocols for the continued care and follow up of patients including identification of key workers for individual patients		Established follow-up structure
Bradley (2013b) ⁸	Eligible Survivors Enrolled in AfterCare	Indicator Rationale: Provides a measure of access to and utilization of the provincial pediatric oncology AfterCare program, which provides systematic follow-up of survivors of childhood cancer across all ages and continuing surveillance for early detection of/ intervention in late effects of treatment, as well as health promotion and education. Definition: a) The proportion of pediatric survivors of pediatric cancer, 0 to 17 years of age, eligible for AfterCare who are enrolled in the program. b) The proportion of adult survivors of pediatric cancer, 18 years of age and older, eligible for AfterCare who are enrolled in the program. Survivors are considered eligible for AfterCare two years after the completion of all therapy, provided they are disease-free and have not relapsed. Survivors are considered enrolled in AfterCare after referral plus attendance at first visit. Indicator Specification: Proportion Numerator: a) Number of pediatric survivors of childhood cancer, 0 to 17 years of age, enrolled in AfterCare. b) Number of adult survivors of childhood cancer, 18 years of age and older, enrolled in AfterCare. Denominator:	Established follow-up structure

		<p>a) Number of pediatric survivors of childhood cancer, 0 to 17 years of age, eligible for enrollment in AfterCare.</p> <p>b) Number of adult survivors of childhood cancer, 18 years of age and older, eligible for enrollment in AfterCare.</p>	
<p>Bradley (2013a)⁹</p>	<p>Eligible survivors enrolled in AfterCare</p>	<p>Indicator Rationale: Provides a measure of access to and utilization of the provincial pediatric oncology AfterCare program, which provides systematic follow-up of survivors of childhood cancer across all ages and continuing surveillance for early detection of/ intervention in late effects of treatment, as well as health promotion and education.</p> <p>Definition:</p> <p>a) The proportion of pediatric survivors of pediatric cancer, 0 to 17 years of age, eligible for AfterCare who are enrolled in the program.</p> <p>b) The proportion of adult survivors of pediatric cancer, 18 years of age and older, eligible for AfterCare who are enrolled in the program.</p> <p>Survivors are considered eligible for AfterCare two years after the completion of all therapy, provided they are disease-free and have not relapsed.</p> <p>Survivors are considered enrolled in AfterCare after referral plus attendance at first visit.</p> <p>Indicator Specification: Proportion</p> <p>Numerator:</p> <p>a) Number of pediatric survivors of childhood cancer, 0 to 17 years of age, enrolled in AfterCare.</p> <p>b) Number of adult survivors of childhood cancer, 18 years of age and older, enrolled in AfterCare.</p> <p>Denominator:</p> <p>a) Number of pediatric survivors of childhood cancer, 0 to 17 years of age, eligible for enrollment in AfterCare.</p> <p>b) Number of adult survivors of childhood cancer, 18 years of age and older, eligible for enrollment in AfterCare.</p>	<p>Established follow-up structure</p>

<p>Bradley (2013a)⁹</p>	<p>Survivors with a survivor care plan</p>	<p>Indicator Rationale: Provides a measure of the efficiency and integration of the pediatric cancer system across the trajectory of disease and age. Survivor care plans allow for the provision of knowledge to and the empowerment of survivors, facilitating self-advocacy, while enabling healthcare providers to best meet the individual needs of survivors.</p> <p>Definition: The proportion of pediatric and adult survivors of childhood cancer enrolled in AfterCare with an individualized and standardized survivor care plan. Indicator Specification: Proportion Numerator: Number of pediatric and adult survivors of childhood cancer enrolled in AfterCare who have been provided with a survivor care plan. Denominator: Number of pediatric and adult survivors of childhood cancer enrolled in AfterCare.</p>	<p>Number/Proportion of survivors of childhood cancer with a survivor care plan</p>
<p>Bradley (2013b)⁸</p>	<p>Survivors with a Survivor Care Plan</p>	<p>Indicator Rationale: Provides a measure of the efficiency and integration of the pediatric cancer system across the trajectory of disease and age. Survivor care plans allow for the provision of knowledge to and the empowerment of survivors, facilitating self-advocacy, while enabling healthcare providers to best meet the individual needs of survivors.</p> <p>Definition: The proportion of pediatric and adult survivors of childhood cancer enrolled in AfterCare with an individualized and standardized survivor care plan. Indicator Specification: Proportion Numerator: Number of pediatric and adult survivors of childhood cancer enrolled in AfterCare who have been provided with a survivor care plan. Denominator: Number of pediatric and adult survivors of childhood cancer enrolled in AfterCare.</p>	<p>Number/Proportion of survivors of childhood cancer with a survivor care plan</p>

NICE (2014) ¹¹	Structure: Evidence of local arrangements to ensure that children [...] who have been treated for cancer have an end-of-treatment summary and care plan that includes agreed follow-up and monitoring arrangements.		Number/Proportion of survivors of childhood cancer with a survivor care plan
NICE (2014) ¹¹	Process: a) The proportion of children [...] completing treatment for cancer who have an end-of-treatment summary and care plan.	Numerator – the number of people in the denominator who have an end-of-treatment summary and care plan. Denominator – the number of children [...] completing treatment for cancer.	Number/Proportion of survivors of childhood cancer with a survivor care plan
NICE (2014) ¹¹	Process: b) The proportion of children [...] treated for cancer who have their end-of-treatment summary and care plan reviewed 5 years after the end of their initial treatment.	Numerator – the number of people in the denominator who have their end-of-treatment summary and care plan reviewed 5 years after the end of their initial treatment. Denominator – the number of children [...] treated for cancer with an end-of-treatment summary and care plan.	Number/Proportion of survivors who have their survivorship care plan reviewed 5 years after the end of treatment
NICE (2005) ⁷	Evidence of care plans for long-term care for all patients		Number/Proportion of survivors of childhood cancer with a survivor care plan
Knops (2012) ³	The physician-in-charge and case manager of follow-up care make in collaboration with other members of the follow-up MDT and the patient a follow-up scheme at the end, one year and 5 years after treatment directed at control of the specific tumor and early detection of relapse or secondary tumours.	Recommendation	Number/Proportion of survivors of childhood cancer with a survivor care plan
Knops (2012) ³	The physician-in-charge and case manager of follow-up care make in collaboration with other members of the follow-up MDT and the patient a follow-up scheme at the end, one year and 5 years after treatment directed at the early detection and treatment of possible side effects, psychosocial and neuropsychological problems after the treatment of childhood cancer.	Recommendation	Number/Proportion of survivors of childhood cancer with a survivor care plan
Knops (2012) ³	The physician-in-charge makes in collaboration with the patient arrangements for transition from paediatric oncology to adult medical oncology when applicable.	Recommendation	Established transition structure
Hord (2014) ²	An established program designed to provide long-term, multidisciplinary follow-up of successfully treated patients at the original treatment center or by a physician led team of health care professionals who are familiar with the potential adverse effects of treatment of childhood cancer; as survivors of		Established transition structure

	childhood cancer move into adulthood, transition to an adult provider may be appropriate		
Volume and numbers			
DKG (2022/2021) ⁵	Primary cases (all first diagnoses of first and second tumors; multiple answers possible; (Pat. with first tumor + cases with second tumors)	Numerator: Primary cases Denominator:-- Target: currently none	Number of cases per year and provider/clinic
DKG (2022/2021) ⁵	Center cases (= primary cases + total cases with initial presentation with recurrence).	Numerator: Center cases Denominator:-- Target ≥ 30	Number of cases per year and provider/clinic
Kowalczyk (2009) ⁴	Requirements of a Paediatric Haematology and/or Oncology Unit	There should be a minimum number of cases that a unit sees to remain efficient and competent. This probably equates to at least 30 new cases per year.	Number of cases per year and provider/clinic
de Rojas (2019) ¹⁰	Number of patients/year		Number of cases per year and provider/clinic
Knops (2013) ¹⁸	Volume of a hospital	<p>...the treatment of more than five cases per year per provider (i.e. either hospital or physician) as 'high volume'</p> <p>...that higher volume hospitals, higher case volume providers, and specialised hospitals are related to the better outcome in paediatric oncology</p> <p>Although there is no consensus about a threshold in paediatric oncology that indicates the transition from low volume providers to high volume providers, for this review we defined the treatment of more than five cases per year per provider (i.e. either hospital or physician) as 'high volume'. This definition of high volume was made after reading the selected studies and based on the encountered volume numbers.</p>	Number of cases per year and provider/clinic

† Abbreviations of publishers: G-BA Federal Joint Committee (Gemeinsamer Bundesausschuss), DKG German Cancer Society (Deutsche Krebsgesellschaft), NICE National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, IQWiG Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Health Care (Institut für Qualität und Wirtschaftlichkeit im Gesundheitswesen)

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